

WP2 – Optimising agroforestry design and management for anticipated benefits and costs of agroforestry innovations

Roadmap 2.0 on Tools for Anticipated Benefits and Costs of Agroforestry Innovations

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Executive summary

In surveys of user needs for agroforestry tools, the request for agroforestry tools to predict the financial benefits and costs of new or existing systems, relative to an existing enterprise, typically features highly. Within the EU funded research project DigitAF (Grant Agreement N° 101059794), one of the objectives was to enhance the quantification of financial benefits and costs of agroforestry systems. This report presents the insights learnt from using four financial tools across six case studies across Europe. The Rekentool was only used to estimate nut yields in the Netherlands case study.

The Farm-SAFE tool is a financial tool designed for researchers to compare the economic and financial benefits and costs of agroforestry compared to tree-only and arable or grassland only systems. It is an Excel-based model that can use annual yield data derived from the biophysical Yield-SAFE model. The Farm-SAFE model was used to compare a silvoarable system in Italy, Finland, and the United Kingdom. In order to use the model in the UK, it was necessary to modify the model so that fruit production by trees could be considered alongside timber and/or fuelwood production. In each case study, the model provides a framework for comparing the benefits and costs of agroforestry with a baseline land use. Although it is a useful research tool, when the tool was examined by the stakeholders in the Italian Living Lab, they considered that the tool was not sufficiently user-friendly for use by farmers and advisors. The model could benefit from more user-friendly interface and database.

The INTACT tool is a financial tool to predict the financial benefits and costs associated with the tree component of agroforestry systems. It does not address the crop and livestock components of agroforestry. The tool, which was developed in Belgium, was successfully used in Italy and the United Kingdom. The users particularly valued the pictures and the step-by-step process of predicting tree establishment costs. In the feedback, it was recognised that tool could benefit from increasing the simulation period beyond 20 years.

The AgroForstRechner model is a tool that describes the yields and economics of short rotation coppice. It was successfully used at the case study site in Germany. The analysis indicated that the sale of woodchips could generate a revenue of about 23,000 € ha⁻¹ over 30 years, with associated costs of about 9,500 € ha⁻¹, resulting in a net margin of about 13,500 € ha⁻¹. The “break-even-price” of woodchips was about 50 € per tonne.

The Final ALS model is a spreadsheet based financial tool, developed in Czechia, to determine the financial benefit and costs of coppice tree belts. It was used in the Dutch and the Czech case studies. With Final-ALS, the potential production of woodchips was calculated for three scenarios of a coppice tree belt system (CTB), producing: 5.5-7.5 m³ in a single row; 10.5-15 m³ in double row; 14.5-20 m³ in triple row. In the Czech case study the model predicted that the net present value tree component of AFS (over 40 years) would be 191,000 € and the

agroforestry system was able to show a positive return by the second year, because of the tree planting subsidy in the second year resulting in an internal rate of return of 70%.

A key demand for all of these financial tools is to make them more “findable”, “accessible”, “interoperable”, and “reusable”. During the DigitAF project, the Farm-SAFE and INTACT tools have been made more readily available, including on the DigitAF tool catalogue ([link](#)).

1 Context

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Our goal is to provide the main actor groups with tools answering their needs, in particular digital tools. The three actor groups that are targeted by DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry - related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisors playing an active role in designing and managing agroforestry systems and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of agroforestry, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of agroforestry in clear and accessible terms.

This report from work-package (WP) 2 deals with optimising agroforestry design and management through the provision of tools for practitioners and farm advisors. Whilst other reports have addressed tree and crop choice, performance, and adaptation potential, this report focuses on the use of financial tools at farm level. An objective of this activity was to enhance the (ex-ante) quantification of the benefits and costs of selected agroforestry practices, relative to selected baseline scenarios, using sites from the DigitAF Living Labs as case studies.

Several DigitAF partners have developed financial and/or economic models for specific types of agroforestry systems. To enhance the exchange of information between the financial tool developers and Living Lab leaders, a “financial tools working group” of DigitAF and external partners was established. A financial tools workshop for project participants was organised in the Netherlands in November 2024, and at Cranfield University in the United Kingdom in February 2025. For each of the six Living Labs, this report contains the qualitative evaluation and financial analysis for the agroforestry innovations for the same farms studied in Milestone 8 entitled “Baseline system and the associated financial benefits and costs” (Cumplido-Marin et al., 2023a). This report also builds on Deliverable 2.3 “Roadmap 1.0 on anticipated benefits and costs of agroforestry innovations” (Cumplido-Marin et al., 2023b), in that it includes a state-of-the-art overview and SWOT analysis of financial tools for agroforestry, modelling results of applying the tools to the real case studies, as well as lessons learnt and a formulation of follow-up steps. Even if this is the final deliverable for task 2.1, some activities (mainly tool improvement) will continue in the last year of the DigitAF project. The deliverable therefore also includes a short description of strategies that will be used for communication and dissemination regarding the final outcomes.

2 Financial tools for agroforestry – overview

2.1 Introduction

The financial tools included in this overview are not an exhaustive list of all financial tools for agroforestry. However it includes a set of tools that were diverse enough to (a) evaluate them with end-users, (b) for tool developers to learn from each other and build plans for future improvement, (c) demonstrate how different tools are useful in different contexts, and (d) are primarily open-access. In each analysis, the selection of tools varies within the report, in accordance with availability of open-source information and familiarity/ownership of the researchers with the tools.

The DigitAF Tool Catalogue ([link](#)) contained 48 tools relevant to agroforestry in June 2025, including a detailed information and a FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reuse) evaluation. As of June 2025, the DigitAF Tool Catalogue includes three financial tools (Farm-SAFE, Rekentool, and INTACT), which are also examined in this report (Table 1). AgroForstRechner is currently not listed in the catalogue, but the plan is that it will be. The six tools are briefly summarised in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 1. Six and four financial tools were assessed in terms of broad characteristics in a meta-data analysis, and in terms of strengths and weaknesses, respectively.

Metadata analysis	Meta-analysis	Strength and weakness analysis
Farm-SAFE v3 https://dspace.lib.cranfield.ac.uk/handle/1826/22350	✓	✓
Rekentool 5.0 voor voedselbossen https://netwerkvoedselbosbouw.nl/rekentool-voedselbossen/	✓	
Agroforstrechner (AF-R) https://agroforst-info.de/agroforstrechner/	✓	✓
INTACT 1.0 https://ilvo.vlaanderen.be/uploads/documents/Agroforestry/Manual-INTACT-1.0_aug2024-1.pdf	✓	✓
Final-ALS	✓	✓
FarmTree https://www.farmtree.earth/home	✓	

Table 2. Description of Farm-SAFE, Rekentool, Agroforstrechner, and INTACT financial tools.

Farm-SAFE v3	Rekentool 5.0 voor voedselbossen [Food forest calculation tool 5.0]
<p>The Rekentool 5.0 voor voedselbossen, developed in the Netherlands, is an Excel file that calculates the financial feasibility of an (agricultural) food forest. The tool can be used as a design tool to assess the profitability of an existing food forest. The tool contains approximately 200 commonly used plant species. The tool can be freely used.</p>	
AgroForstRechner [AgroForestCalculator]	INTACT 1.0
<p>INTACT (INTERactive Agroforestry Cost-benefit Tool) is a tool developed in Belgium to evaluate the costs and benefits for the trees and shrubs in an agroforestry project. The tool focuses specifically on the costs and benefits related to trees and shrubs (without crops and without animals) within agroforestry systems, making it a partial financial analysis. INTACT is thus not intended for integral business analysis.</p>	

Table 3. Description of the Final-ALS and FarmTree tool

Final-ALS [AgroLesnické Systémy]	FarmTree
<p data-bbox="810 757 1380 1057">The FarmTree Tool is an online quantitative agroforestry tools with different modules (plant growth; competition for space, water, nutrients; soil carbon, fertility and hydrology). It is managed as a commercial product and the user needs to register. It includes a benefits and cost module, that allows a comparison of different scenarios.</p>	

2.2 Metadata

A metadata spreadsheet was created to collate the main characteristics of the six models. The main points are highlighted in Table 4. The complete set of data is included in Appendix A. Whereas Farm-SAFE is primarily a research tool, the other five tools have been designed for use by farmers and advisors. Each of the tools has been designed to enable a financial cost benefit analysis; although this is only a partial cost-benefit analysis for INTACT. INTACT was designed to determine the costs of the tree system, Rekentool was designed to describe the costs and benefits of the tree system, and the other four models also allow comparison with an arable system.

Table 4. An overview of some of the main characteristics of the six financial models as assessed by six developers or users^a

Tool name	Farm-SAFE v3	Rekentool	AgroForst-Rechner (AF-R)	INTACT 1.0	FINAL-ALS	FarmTree
Target group and objective						
Primary target end user	Researcher		Farmer or Advisor	Farmer or Advisor	Farmer, Advisor, Investor, Researcher	Farmer, Advisor, Investor, Researcher
Financial cost benefit analysis	Yes	Yes		Yes (partial)	Yes	Yes
Temporal and spatial						
Timestep	Annual	Annual	Annual	Annual	Annual	Monthly and Annual
Default simulation period	60 years	50 years	80 years	20 years	30 years	50 years
Temporal system boundary	Planting to tree harvest	Whole life cycle		Whole life cycle	Whole life cycle	Whole life cycle
Discount methodology	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes.	Yes.
Spatial scale	Plot and Farm	Plot	Plot	Plot	Plot	Plot and Farm
Tree component	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Crop component	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Comparison with agriculture	Yes				Yes	Yes
Comparison with forestry	Yes					Yes
Software						
Software/user interface	Microsoft Excel		Excel (old version) / Python (new)	Excel and Oracle Apex	Microsoft Excel	C#, Blazor
Outputs						
Cost	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Revenue	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Gross margin	Yes	Yes		No	Yes	Yes
Workload	Yes	No		Yes	No	Yes
NPV (net present value)	Yes			Yes	Yes	Yes
User manual						
User Manual available	Yes		https://agroforst-info.de/agroforstrechner/	Agroforestry Planner - Agroforestry	Methodology+ manual Under preparation (XII/25)	

^a: Developers or users: Paul Burgess (Farm-SAFE), Waas Thissen (Rekentool), Rico Hübner (AgroForstRechner), Sarah Carton (INTACT 1.0), FINAL-ALS (Jaroslav Knápek, Jan Weger) and FarmTree (Marina Alarcón, Frank van Schoubroeck).

2.3 Analysis of strengths and weaknesses

Four of the financial tools were evaluated in terms of various strengths and weaknesses by the DigitAF research team from the perspective of an end-user (Table 5) and a tool developer (Table 6). Farm-SAFE, INTACT, and Final ALS were evaluated by tool developers/researchers (Laura Cumplido-Marin, Sarah Carton, Jan Weger) in February 2025 during the UK financial tool workshop, and AgroForstRechner was separately evaluated by Rico Hübner. In general, the Farm-SAFE financial tool (which was developed as a research tool) was not rated user-friendly for an end-user and it relied on bespoke data inputs. By contrast the INTACT tool to determine the costs of different tree systems was considered user-friendly, but there was limited flexibility in altering data inputs (Table 5).

Table 5. Qualitative evaluation **for end user**, as perceived by tool developers (satisfactory: ✓; good: ✓✓; very good: ✓✓✓; not possible: X).

Parameters	Farm-SAFE ⁱⁱ	AgroForst-Rechner ^{iv}	INTACT ⁱ	Final ALS ⁱⁱⁱ	Comments
User friendliness	✓ ^a	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓ ^a	^a Challenging for non-experienced users, lot of input data needed
Availability of default data	✓ ^c	✓✓✓ ^b	✓✓✓ ^b	✓ ^c	^b Lots of parameters predefined ^c Data is case specific
Data storage	✓✓✓ ^d	✓✓✓ ^d	✓	✓✓✓ ^d	^d Data is saved and stored on spreadsheet
Data input flexibility	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓✓	^e Most values can be changed from default to individual, these can be stored and recalled later
Scenario comparison	✓✓✓	✓✓	X ^f	✓✓	^f Only way to create 2 scenarios is to open a 2 nd tab in incognito mode
Sensitivity analysis options	✓✓ ^g	✓✓✓	X	✓✓	^g Some possible
Presentation of results and export options	✓✓	✓	✓✓	✓	ⁱⁱⁱ It could be easily improved ^{iv} Mostly as time series/tables, however export function allows to create graphs

When the DigitAF team assessed the strengths and weaknesses of the four tools from the perspective of a developer (Table 6), rather than an end-user, the results are broadly the same as observed in Table 5. Again, there was a trade-off between the availability of default data and the flexibility of entering one's own data. Because the INTACT model is primarily a tree cost model, it does not have the capacity for scenario comparison nor to consider a range of agroforestry systems, contrary to the other three models.

Table 6. Qualitative evaluation for tool developers as perceived by tool developers (satisfactory: ✓; good: ✓✓; very good: ✓✓✓; not possible: X).

Parameters	Farm-SAFE ⁱⁱ	AgroForst-Rechner ^{iv}	INTACT ⁱ	Final ALS ⁱⁱⁱ	Comments
Availability of default data	✓ ^b	✓✓ ^a	✓✓✓ ^a	✓ ^b	^a Lots of parameters predefined ^b Data are case specific
Data storage	✓✓✓ ^c	✓✓ ^c	✓ ^d	✓✓✓ ^c	^c Data is saved and stored on spreadsheet ^d User inputs only stored during the time that the user in on the website
Data input flexibility	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓✓	
Applicable agroforestry systems	✓✓ ^g	✓✓ ^f	X ^e	✓✓	^e No crop/animal component ^f First version was developed only for short rotation coppice systems ^g Modelling of fruit and nut trees is currently being developed.
Scenario comparison	✓✓	✓✓	X ^h	✓✓	^h Only way to create 2 scenarios is to open a 2 nd tab in incognito mode and look at results from both systems
Sensitivity analysis options	✓✓	✓✓	X	✓	
Presentation of results and export options	✓✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓	

2.4 Decision tree for selecting financial tools for agroforestry

Based on the components considered by each tool, a decision support tree was constructed to indicate the possible most appropriate model. For example, if the focus is a business plan, the FarmTree would appear to be the most appropriate tool (Figure 1). If the focus is only on the cost of the trees, then INTACT could be an appropriate model. However, if a consideration of the interactions between the trees and crop yields is of interest, then other models would be appropriate. None of the models specifically includes the economics of livestock management.

Figure 1. Decision tree for modelling agroforestry systems, focusing on the (1) type of system, (2) scale, and (3) application. The colours indicate the country in which the tool has been developed.

2.5 Application of the models to six Living Labs

The practical application of five financial models was examined across six Living Lab case studies across Europe: Italy, Germany, the Netherlands, Finland, Czechia, and the United Kingdom (Table 7). Living Labs have been defined as “user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings” (Malmberg et al., 2017). Creating the Living Labs was the first step into the co-creation and collaboration process with representative stakeholders from the whole value chain of agroforestry products. Since then, we have been in continuous communication with the Living Lab participants in each country, consulting with them whenever needed, have used their expertise to progress each step of the project, and have considered their opinions and feedback in the development of the project deliverables and forward plan.

Table 7. Financial models tested across six Living Lab case study sites.

Location	Models tested
Italy	Farm-SAFE, INTACT
Germany	AgroForstRechner
The Netherland	Farm-SAFE, Rekentool ^a , Final-AFS ^a
Finland	Farm-SAFE
Czech Republic	Final-ALS
United Kingdom	Farm-SAFE, INTACT

^a: For biophysical assessments

3 Italian case study

3.1 Background to case study and assumptions

The case study chosen within the Italian Living Lab was the 40 ha Arnino Long Term Experiment at the Enrico Avanzi Research Centre in Tuscany (Figure 2, Figure 3). The experiment was set up in 2017 to compare four different systems:

- i. arable with 3-year crop rotation;
- ii. silvoarable with 3-year crop rotation;
- iii. mixed system with 7 years crop rotation;
- iv. and agrosilvopastoral with 7 years crop rotation.

For the financial analysis only the arable and the silvoarable systems were selected for comparison. Both systems are managed with a 3-year arable crop rotation composed of durum wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf.), Faba bean (*Vicia faba* var. minor Beck), and sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*), which was first cropped in 2017-2018. Within the silvoarable system two different densities of poplar were established in 2019:

- 30 m of distance between tree rows: north part of fields 21, 22, and 23 and fields 47, 48, 49.
- 15 m of distance between tree rows: south part of fields 21, 22, and 23.

Figure 2. Aerial view of the Arnino Long Term Experiment. Arable fields are coloured in blue (id: 10, 11, 12, 32, 33, 34, 51, 52, and 53); silvoarable fields (id: 21, 22, 23, 47, 48, and 49) are coloured in green; control field for the forest system (poplar only) is coloured in orange (id: 1).

The aim of the financial analysis for this case study is to evaluate the financial feasibility and the future revenue of the arable, silvoarable, and control forest to try to determine which system guarantees stable incomes in future years.

Figure 3. The silvoarable system with poplar at Arnino (Photo: Matteo Finocchi)

3.2 Qualitative evaluation

3.2.1 Confirming the agroforestry innovation/system of interest

The first set of questions aims to provide a general description of the agroforestry system of interest.

- How much land have you used for the agroforestry system?
The arable fields occupy 5.41 ha. The silvoarable fields with low tree density (one single row of poplars) occupy 3.76 ha. The silvoarable system with high tree density (two rows of poplars) occupy 1.65 ha, and the forest system field occupies 0.56 ha.
- Which tree species did you choose?
*Several clones of poplars (*Populus spp.*) and English oak (*Quercus robur L.*). The clones were tested to determine which ones are more adapted to Mediterranean conditions.*
- Have they all grown well?
Poplars grew slowly in the first years after planting. Despite oaks being a slow growing species, they are still suffering and most of them have died, their establishment failed.
- Would you use the same tree species again?
The best performing poplar clones could be replanted but planting oak is discouraged.
- What density did you plant the poplars at? Do you think you will thin them during the rotation? If so, in which year?
System with lower density: trees were planted every 10 m within the same row, on a single line, 30 m apart between tree rows. Oaks are planted between poplar, 5 m from them. All

rows have a drainage ditch next to the trees. In the high density system: an additional only poplar row was planted in the centre of the alley at 7.5 m spacing between trees within the same row.

- How do you manage the tree strip area? Do you still have to manage it in any particular way?

Weeding once a year.

- What crops/livestock are you using in the rows between the trees? Do you think this will evolve over time as the trees grow bigger?

No livestock is introduced in any of the treatments. Arable rotational system: 3-year rotation (durum wheat, sorghum, and faba bean). A type of vetch (Vicia villosa) is planted after the sorghum as cover crop.

3.2.2 Perceived advantages and disadvantages of the agroforestry system

During a visit of seven farmers and consultants to the Living Lab site, the participants were asked, using Mentimeter, to identify the potential advantages and disadvantages of silvoarable systems. Table 8 and Figure 4 present a summary of the reported feedback, while the full set of answers is included in the Appendix B.

Table 8. Perceived benefits and disadvantages of the silvoarable system at Arnino

Benefits of system	Disadvantages of system
<i>Biodiversity</i>	<i>Decrease of yields</i>
<i>Diversification</i>	<i>Mechanization and harvesting</i>
<i>Optimization and efficiency</i>	<i>Cost of implant</i>
<i>Ecosystem services</i>	<i>No supporting policies/funding</i>
<i>Soil structure and increase of soil organic matter</i>	<i>Shade</i>
<i>Biological control</i>	<i>Tree row management</i>
<i>Sustainability</i>	
<i>Landscape</i>	

a) Benefits

b) Disadvantages

Figure 4. Word clouds using Mentimeter when seven Living Lab participants were asked to describe a) the benefits and b) the disadvantages of agroforestry.

From the results in Table 8, the main perceived advantages of agroforestry include increasing biodiversity, diversifying production and improving the landscape. The perceived disadvantages included issues related to mechanisation and low returns.

3.3 Financial analysis using Farm-SAFE

One of the perceived advantages and disadvantages of the silvoarable system was related to the financial question of low returns. At the Italian site, the first selected financial tool was the Farm-SAAFE model. The Farm-SAFE model allows a comparison of monoculture systems (arable and forest systems) with agroforestry systems, and much of the required data needed to populate Farm-SAFE was available. After discussion, the following three questions were identified to be of interest:

- Which of the three systems (arable, silvoarable, forest) is the most profitable after completing a production cycle of 18 years (tree rotation)?
- Which tree density guarantees a higher Land Equivalent Ratio?

An advantage of the Farm-SAFE model is the capacity to compare the benefit and costs of different systems (Table 4). This comparison of agroforestry with a crop-only and a tree-only system also enables the calculation of a land equivalent ration (LER). One way of quantifying the benefits of agroforestry is by using the Land Equivalent Ratio (LER), defined as “the ratio of the area under sole cropping to the area under intercropping (or agroforestry), at the same level of management that gives an equal amount of yield” (Ong and Kho, 2015; Paul et al., 2017). Equation 1 (Graves et al., 2010) is used for the calculation the LER.

$$LER = \frac{\text{tree silvoarable yield}}{\text{tree monoculture yield}} + \frac{\text{crop silvoarable yield}}{\text{crop monoculture yield}} \quad \text{Equation 1.}$$

where: tree silvoarable yield = harvested timber biomass in the silvoarable system (t ha⁻¹)
tree monoculture yield = harvested timber biomass in the monoculture system (forest) (t ha⁻¹)
crop silvoarable yield = harvested crop biomass in the silvoarable system (t ha⁻¹)
crop monoculture yield = harvested crop biomass in the monoculture system (arable) (t ha⁻¹)

3.3.1 Yield, costs, and price data

The yield data used within the Farm-SAFE financial tool was derived using the Yield-SAFE model. The Yield-SAFE model is a bio-physical model able to predict crop and tree yields in conventional systems (forest and arable) and silvoarable agroforestry systems, that incorporates local soil and climate data. The calibration of the Yield-SAFE model was completed using recorded data from the Arnino site, literature data, and consultation with experts. Characteristics of the experimental fields used for calibration and data collection are reported in Table 9.

Table 9. Characteristics of each field of the arable and silvoarable system at Arnino.

System (Field n.)	Tree row length (m)	Total area (ha)	Trees (n)	Tree density (trees ha ⁻¹)	Crop rotation (first crop)
Forest					
(36)		0.56	132	237	
Arable		5.41			
(10, 32, 51)		2.06			Durum wheat
(11, 38, 52)		1.64			Faba bean
(12, 34, 53)		1.71			Sorghum
Silvoarable - low density		3.76			
(21, 47)	486	1.26	32	36	Durum wheat
(22, 48)	476	1.41	42	30	Faba bean
(23, 49)	445	1.09	42	37	Sorghum
Silvoarable - high density		1.65			
(21)	144	0.46	45	70	Durum wheat
(22)	199	0.56	42	75	Faba bean
(23)	201	0.63	40	67	Sorghum

During the first years after establishment, crop losses were registered due to wild animals, mainly wild boar. Thus, part of the trial was fenced in 2021 to avoid further damages. These values were considered outliers and therefore not taken into consideration for the calibration of Yield-SAFE.

3.3.1.1 Arable component

The calibration of the crop component was performed using measured data (Figure 5) and crop parameters were adjusted according to values present within the literature.

The crops were assumed to cover 100% of the fields in the arable system. In the silvoarable system, crop cover was calculated considering the percentage of the area occupied by the tree rows (width and length). Crop cover varied between 89-92% in the low-density system and between 82-84% in the high-density system. Calibrated and projected crop yields are illustrated in Figure 5, where straight lines represent average productions.

All operations conducted from 2018 to 2023 in the selected fields at the trial site were recorded (

Table 10). Some operations were conducted by the experimental farm employees while others were conducted by contractors. The regional Italian price list for agricultural operations was used to estimate the cost of operations performed for crop cultivation (CAI Agromec, 2022). A summary of the input of costs is reported in

Table 10. These costs include a cost of labour of 19.24 € h⁻¹ for the Tuscany region, rounded up at 20 € h⁻¹. Crop prices used for revenue determination within Farm-SAFE were: 229.50 € t⁻¹ for durum wheat, 237.50 € t⁻¹ for faba bean, and 135.0 € t⁻¹ for sorghum (Borsa merci, 2022).

Figure 5. Results of the calibration: predicted and measured crop yields in a) the arable system, and b) the low density (36, 30, 37 trees ha⁻¹), and c) high density (70, 75, 67 trees ha⁻¹) silvoarable systems.

Table 10. Summary of variable costs related to crop operations conducted at the case-study.

	Variable cost	Durum wheat	Field beans	Sorghum	
Seed	Cost (€/kg)	0.97	0.79	90.00	
	Seeding rate (kg/ha)	250	150	1	
	<i>Seed cost (€/ha)</i>	242.50	118.50	90.00	
Fertilisers	Mineral fertiliser (TSP)				
	Cost (€/kg of fertiliser)	0.41	0.41	0.41	
	Application rate (kg/ha)	150.00	100.00	100.00	
	<i>Fertiliser cost A (€/ha)</i>	60.75	40.50	40.50	
	Mineral fertiliser (NH ₄ NO ₃)				
	Cost (€/kg of fertiliser)	0.26	0.26	0.26	
	Application rate (kg/ha)	100.00			
	<i>Fertiliser cost B (€/ha)</i>	25.70	0.00	0.00	
	Mineral fertiliser (Urea)				
	Cost (€/kg of fertiliser)	0.39	0.39	0.39	
	Application rate (kg/ha)	100.00	0.00	100.00	
	<i>Fertiliser cost C (€/ha)</i>	39.30	0.00	39.30	
	Average cost inserted in Farm-SAFE (€/kg)	0.352	0.40	0.40	
	Application rate used in Farm-SAFE (€/ha)	350.00	100.00	200.00	
Crop Protection	Adjuvants				
	Cost (€/litre)	5.00	0.00	0.00	
	Application rate (litres/ha)	1.00	0.00	0.00	
	Number of applications	1	0	0	
	<i>Adjuvant cost (€/ha)</i>	5.00	0.00	0.00	
	Herbicides				
	Cost (€/litre)	35.00	70.00	0.00	
	Application rate (litres/ha)	1.00	2.50	0.00	
	Number of applications	1	1	0	
	<i>Herbicide cost (€/ha)</i>	35.00	175.00	0.00	
	Fungicides				
	Cost (€/litre)	70.00	0.00	0.00	
	Application rate (litres/ha)	1.00	0.00	0.00	
	Number of applications	1	0	0	
	<i>Fungicide cost (€/ha)</i>	70.00	0.00	0.00	
		Average cost of single application inserted in Farm-SAFE (€/applications)	36.67		
		Total number of applications	3.00		
		<i>Total cost inserted in Farm-SAFE (€/ha)</i>	110.00		
	Total variable costs (€/ha)	478.25	334.00	169.80	
Fixed costs: Labour	Labour time (h/ha)	4.90	3.30	8.10	
	Labour rate (€/h)	10.00	10.00	10.00	
	<i>Labour cost (€/ha)</i>	49.00	33.00	81.00	
Fixed costs: machinery	Working time (h/ha)	4.90	3.30	8.10	
	Machinery rate (€/h)	144.29	58.36	76.62	
	<i>Machinery cost (€/ha)</i>	707.02	192.59	620.62	
	Total general costs (€/ha)	756.02	225.59	701.62	
	Total fixed costs (€/ha)	756.02	225.59	701.62	
	Total costs (€/ha)	1234.27	559.59	871.42	

3.3.1.2 *Tree component*

Yield-SAFE allows to simulate the growth of only one tree species at the time. Because of the failure to establish oak, oak was excluded from the simulation of yields with Yield-SAFE, accounting only for poplar. We assumed that the competition between poplar trees and crops was low.

The rate of poplar growth changes greatly according to climatic conditions, location, and available resources. Harvesting poplar for timber production is profitable when the diameter at breast height (DBH) reaches at least 22 cm (Chiarabaglio, personal communication, May 2025). Some examples of poplar growth in silvoarable systems are found at the Loughgall trial site, located in Northern Ireland (UK) where poplars reached 21 cm of diameter in 10 years and 25 cm in 13 years (Giannitsopoulos et al., 2025) and the Veneto Agricoltura trial site, located in the Po valley (IT) where poplars reached 24 cm of diameter in 4 years (Piotto et al., 2024).

As the data shows, edaphoclimatic conditions (in particular temperatures and water availability) play an important role in the growth rate of poplars. In our case study, water is a limiting factor during summer; while in winter soils have a shallow water-table due to the proximity to a river and the sea. High temperatures in the summer months further limit poplar growth due to increased stress conditions. This has a serious effect in the growth of trees, negatively impacting the financial return of the investment. Therefore, the determination of the tree rotation is variable according to the site. As far as we know, there are few poplar plantations in central Italy and generally they are placed close to rivers. There is no reference value available for the duration of the tree rotation.

A diameter of 40 cm was considered suitable for cutting (Chiarabaglio, personal communication, May 2025); this diameter was reached after 18 years in the simulations with Yield-SAFE. In terms of recorded data from poplar trees in the experimental fields, heights were collected for the period 2021-2023 and circumference and diameter for the period 2023-2025. Average values from this datasets were used for the calibration of the forest and silvoarable systems within Yield-SAFE. Figure 6 shows the results of the calibration of the poplars in the forest system, and Figure 7 shows the results of the calibration of the poplars in the silvoarable system at low and high density.

Figure 6. Comparison of the observed and predicted a) diameter, b) height, and c) timber volume of a poplar tree in the forest system (tree density of 236 trees ha⁻¹).

The costs related to the tree component and information needed to complete the Excel spreadsheet “Trecost” and “Treevalue” within Farm-SAFE are summarised in Table 11, information gathered in consultation with experts from CREA (Chiarabaglio, personal communication, May 2025). Figure 8 shows the increasing standing value of poplar timber along the years (Chiarabaglio, personal communication, May 2025).

Figure 7. Results of the calibration of the a) and b) diameter, c) and d) the height, and e) and f) the timber volume of the poplars in a silvoarable system at a density of 36,30,37 trees ha⁻¹ and 70,75, 67 trees ha⁻¹ respectively.

Figure 8. Standing value of poplar timber relative to the volume of the timber (m³) used in "Treevalue" Spreadsheet within Farm-SAFE.

Table 11. Summary of costs related to the tree component inserted in Farm-SAFE.

Tree component costs	Unit	Value
Establishment		
Cost of plant	(€ tree ⁻¹)	2.50
Labour for ground preparation	(hr ha ⁻¹)	4.0
Labour for marking out	(hr ha ⁻¹)	3.5
Labour for planting trees	min/tree	6.00
Maintenance		
Year of first weeding	year	1
Year of last weeding	years	10
Annual labour for weeding	min/tree	0.60
Pruning		
Height at first prune	(m)	3.0
Minutes per tree at first prune	(min/tree)	1.00
Height at last prune	(m)	7.0
Minutes per tree at last prune	(min/tree)	2.0
Removal of pruning	(min/tree)	0.40
Clear felling		
Labour	(min/tree)	18.0
Removal of tree	(min/m ³)	4.0

3.3.2 Calculated yields and margins

Results are displayed as discounted cumulative net margin that include the stand values when mono-cropping systems (forest and arable systems) are compared with the silvoarable systems (low and high tree density). The comparison between the low density silvoarable system and the high density silvoarable system is made comparing the yearly net present value.

3.3.2.1 Yield results

The predicted yields for faba bean, durum wheat and sorghum in the arable rotation ranged between 2 and 5 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Figure 9). The timber yield in the forest system was predicted to reach 275 m³ ha⁻¹ by year 18 (Figure 10). The predicted arable yields in the low density silvoarable systems ranged between 2 and 6 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, and between 2 and 6.5 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in the high density system (Figure 11). The timber yield in the low and high density silvoarable systems reached about 50 m³ ha⁻¹ and 100 m³ ha⁻¹ by year 18 respectively (Figure 11).

Figure 9. Predicted arable crop yields in the arable system.

Figure 10. Predicted timber volume in the forest system.

Figure 11. Projected yields of the silvoarable systems (left = low density; right = high density).

The results of the Land Equivalent Ratio (LER) calculations are shown in Table 12. The LER is higher than 1 in all the silvoarable fields, both for low and high density of poplars. A LER higher than 1 means that the intercropping between tree and crops is predicted to result in higher yields compared to growing the trees and crops as separate monocultures. In this case study, a tree density of 60-70 trees ha⁻¹ resulted in a mean LER of 1.28, compared to a mean LER of 1.14 for a tree density of 36-37 trees ha⁻¹. The LER tends to be higher in the initial stages of a silvoarable system when the trees are small.

Table 12. Predicted land equivalent ratios (LER) for silvoarable systems with low and high tree densities and three arable rotations.

Field	Field: 10, 32, 51, 21, 47		Field: 11, 33, 52, 22, 48		Field: 12, 34, 53, 23, 49	
Rotation	Rotation 1: Durum wheat-Sorghum-Faba bean		Rotation 2: Faba bean-Durum wheat-Sorghum		Rotation 3: Sorghum-Faba bean-Durum wheat	
Tree density (tree ha⁻¹)	36	70	30	75	37	67
LER tree density	Low	High	Low	High	Low	High
Year						
1	1.15	1.30	1.13	1.32	1.19	1.36
2	1.35	1.64	1.13	1.32	1.16	1.27
3	1.13	1.26	1.38	1.69	1.13	1.23
4	1.13	1.26	1.13	1.32	1.17	1.32
5	1.21	1.43	1.12	1.31	1.10	1.20
6	1.11	1.22	1.17	1.41	1.10	1.20
7	1.11	1.22	1.14	1.30	1.30	1.52
8	1.36	1.55	1.10	1.26	1.09	1.18
9	1.15	1.27	1.14	1.38	1.10	1.20
10	1.11	1.22	1.09	1.25	1.23	1.41
11	1.25	1.38	1.08	1.22	1.10	1.19
12	1.13	1.24	1.25	1.64	1.09	1.17
13	1.09	1.18	1.08	1.22	1.28	1.41
14	1.16	1.30	1.06	1.15	1.12	1.20
15	1.08	1.16	1.16	1.34	1.05	1.10
16	1.02	1.06	1.05	1.14	1.16	1.27
17	1.25	1.44	1.01	1.05	1.10	1.16
18	1.05	1.11	1.07	1.12	1.00	1.01
Average	1.16	1.29	1.13	1.30	1.14	1.24

3.3.3 Financial results

The discounted cumulative net margins were plotted to compare the monoculture systems (forest and arable system) with the silvoarable systems, both low and high tree density (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Results of the discounted cumulative net margins of the monoculture systems (forest and arable) and silvoarable system with a) low and b) high tree density. The green area indicates a positive profit while the red area indicate a negative profit.

On the basis of the assumptions, the most profitable system at the end of 18 years was the forestry system with a value of about €10,000 ha⁻¹. Initially the forest system runs at a loss, but by year 13, the system (including the standing value of the trees) becomes profitable. At this time the predicted tree diameter was 26 cm. This result is in line with the expert we consulted who highlighted that harvesting poplar timber is profitable only when poplar

reaches diameters over 22 cm. For the arable system, profits are negative in the third rotation until year 6, while rotation 1 and 2 are slightly positive. The maximum profit obtained in the arable system is about 1500 € ha⁻¹. When trees are integrated within the system, the cumulative net margin increases up to 2500 € ha⁻¹ in a low tree density system and up to 5000 € ha⁻¹ in a high tree density system.

In this initial analysis the value of the silvoarable system was predicted to decrease in year 18. It is presumed that this is due to a negative net margin in year 18 which is related to the cost of harvesting the trees (Figure 13). This appears to be an erroneous result. One way to address this is to calculate a “standing value” for timber volume.

Figure 13. Annual discounted net margins of the low and high tree density of the silvoarable systems.

3.3.4 Reflections after modelling with Farm-SAFE

The modelling conducted using Yield-SAFE and Farm-SAFE tools provides a good overview of system dynamics and future production of monoculture systems and silvoarable systems. The results obtained from Yield-SAFE predicted that a higher tree density (67-75 trees ha⁻¹) resulted in a higher land equivalent ratio than the low tree density (30-37 trees ha⁻¹) scenario. Moreover, the financial analysis conducted shows that the inclusion of a second row of trees increases net margins. However, although there was a positive LER, in terms of financial analysis, on the basis of the indicated assumptions, planting a monoculture of poplar was the most profitable system. A financial analysis of any agroforestry system can be an iterative process. The development of the model within Yield-SAFE and Farm-SAFE provides a framework for analysing the reasons why one particular system is predicted to be more productive or profitable than another, and then adapt the systems to increase profitability.

3.4 Financial analysis of tree costs using INTACT

3.4.1 Introduction to INTACT

The second tool used in the Italian Living Lab was the INTACT tool which was originally developed in Belgium. There it was developed as a dynamic decision support tool to provide information regarding the costs and the benefits of establishing trees on farmland, and predict when the trees would reach a break-even point (the moment when revenue offsets costs). It does this as a user-friendly web tool that allows the user to interactively estimate costs and benefits of trees and shrubs following a step-by-step approach. At the same time, the tool offers valuable (visual) information to the user during key decision-making moments. Hence the tool uses i) visual aids to clarify options to the user (Figure 14), ii) step-by-step guidance with question mark buttons to give explanations to the user, and iii) default data. Hence users only need to alter context-specific values that they know, such as the user info (Carton et al. 2024) and product price.

Figure 14. Visual aid showing different options for tree guards including background information in the web tool of INTACT.

3.4.2 Model and assumptions

For the financial modelling with INTACT, several financial metrics obtained from Excel were used, including the net present value (NPV; units: € ha⁻¹), internal rate of return (IRR; units: %), investment cost (excluding VAT; units: €), payback period (units: n), and the cost: benefit ratio. The net present value (NPV) is calculated using Equation 2:

$$NPV = (r, \sum FDCF[\text{Year1}:\text{Year20}]) + FCF[\text{Year0}] \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where: r = discount rate; FDCF = free discounted cash flow; FCF = free cash flow

The internal rate of return (IRR) is calculated using Equation 3. It is the discount rate that makes the NPV of all cash flows equal to zero, giving an indication of the profitability of your potential investment (trees/shrubs).

$$\text{IRR}(\sum \text{FCF}[\text{Year0:Year20}])=0 \quad \text{Equation 3.}$$

The payback period, calculated using Equation 4 is the length of time (in years) that it takes to recover the cost of investment of the newly established trees. It is the number of years (from year 0 to year 20), during which the cumulative free cash flow (CFCF) is still negative. For instance, if the CFCF is negative for Years 0-6 and turns positive in Year 7, the payback period is 7 years:

$$\text{Payback period} = \text{COUNTIF}(\sum \text{CFCF}[\text{Year0:Year20}]; '<0')$$
 Equation 4.

Assumptions

There are a number of assumptions that are incorporated into the INTACT model, and some additional assumptions were needed to apply it to the Arnino silvoarable system. All assumptions can be fully read in the manual of INTACT 1.0 (Carton et al., 2024).

- Tree-crop and tree-animal interactions affecting tree yield are not considered. Positive side effects, such as natural pest control or nutrient recycling, are also not taken into account.
- INTACT was initially built to perform a cost-benefit analysis of an alley cropping system but it is possible to use it for other tree spatial arrangements. It is essential that the total tree row surface is calculated well, so INTACT can calculate costs accordingly.
- Pricing for planting materials is based on tree nursery catalogues from 2023. With the Excel INTACT version 1.1, it was possible to adjust the prices but this is not the case for the web tool.
- The surface area of the plot is used to calculate the number of trees per hectare.
- The surface area of the tree rows is used for calculations related to terrain modifications or other planting activities. This distinction was made because these calculations should only be applied to the tree area and not to the entire field.
- Labour (units: h) is based on figures from the 2020 KWIN Standards Book from Wageningen University (van Raffe and de Jong, 2020). INTACT allows users to select their own wage, with the model applying the user's chosen wage to the time required for an activity.
- Machine costs are based on the figures from the 2020 KWIN Standards Book (van Raffe and de Jong, 2020), but an adjustment of those figures was necessary each time to take out the labour costs, as these are budgeted separately in INTACT (see previous point).
- INTACT calculates labour for terrain modifications based on an average reflecting three soil types (sand, loam, clay) from the 2020 KWIN Standards Book (van Raffe and de Jong,

2020). At the moment, it is not possible to let the user choose a soil type to adapt the calculations.

- INTACT calculates fruit and nut yield linearly based on 1) the year at which the tree has reached its maximum production (peak year), and 2) applying the “40-60-80-100% rule” i.e. a simplification of reality implying that yield linearly increases to the peak year and afterward the yield is constant. A tree’s peak production year represents 100%. In the year prior, it produces 80%, followed by 60% two years before the peak, and 40% three years before. No yield has been calculated for any years earlier than that. The years following the peak production year are maintained at 100% production through to year 20, the final year of the simulation. Note that the peak year is species-dependent which could be disadvantageous for certain species (e.g. sugar maple) in a timeline of 20 years. Another point of discussion is that yields for slow-growing trees should be more gradually increasing than the 40-60-80-100% rule, whereas this could be the opposite for fast-growing trees. We average this out by applying the 40-60-80-100% rule to all species.
- INTACT assumes that 100% of the tree products is sold.
- Benefits considered are freshly harvested fruits and nuts. Processed fruits and nuts are not included in INTACT 1.0.
- To give insight into wood production, wood yield is shown in a separate table in the final step. However, wood yield is not taken into account in INTACT’s cost-benefit analysis. The reason for this is that the financial value of wood yield is volatile and we have yet to work out a more reliable methodology for this. For the Italian Living Lab, the Excel model INTACT version 1.1 was used as wood was the only marketable product.
- We assume that the user completes the steps as accurately as possible to get a realistic estimate of the costs and benefits of his scenario. We advise the user to consult INTACT 1.0 Manual if more background information and web tool tips are desired.

3.4.3 Yield, costs and price data

3.4.3.1 Tree component

Since the Italian Living Lab focuses on wood production, wood yield estimations were performed based on adjusting diameter at breast height (DBH) curves from the CARAT tool (Pardon et al., 2024). For this, the following steps were taken:

1. Transform the DBH growth curve (cm yr^{-1}) into a biomass growth curve (kg yr^{-1})
2. Transform the biomass growth curve (kg yr^{-1}) into wood volume growth ($\text{m}^3 \text{yr}^{-1}$)
3. Adjust the right wood density for each species - 370 kg/m^3 (poplar) and 580 kg/m^3 (oak)

This resulted in the cumulative wood yield per tree for poplar and oak separately (Figure 15). Figure 15 shows that at Year 20, the end of INTACT’s simulation time, wood yield is around 2.68 m^3 per poplar tree, and 0.29 m^3 per oak tree. For oak, however, it would imply that harvesting wood after 20 years is too soon. INTACT’s simulation time is too short to make proper oak yield projections. Regarding the benefits, the wood prices were manually adjusted in INTACT to $\text{€}32.57 \text{ m}^{-3}$ for poplar, and $\text{€}300 \text{ m}^{-3}$ for oak.

Figure 15. Yield profile of poplar (blue) and oak (orange) for 50 years. Note that INTACT’s simulation time is 20 years (green line).

For modelling the Italian case study, we used a combination of default data (all referenced within INTACT) and data from conversations with the farm managers to identify the costs and benefits of production. Table 13 shows the general input data that is needed from the user to calculate costs and benefits with INTACT.

Table 13. General input data from user of the Italian case study.

Inputs	Units	Value
Surface agroforestry plot	(ha)	3.28
Number of trees	(n)	284
Tree density	(n ha ⁻¹)	86.59
Expected surface of tree rows	(ha)	0.355
Gross salary - contractor	(€ h ⁻¹)	19.24
Gross salary – seasonal labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	19.24
Gross salary - farmer	(€ h ⁻¹)	19.24

Inputs costs used to model the Italian case study with INTACT are summarized in Table 14, mostly INTACT’s default data. The background colouring refers to only default data (grey), a combination of default data and farm data (orange), and only farm data (no colour) was used to calculate costs. The arable costs are described in Table 15.

Table 14. Input data of costs for tree component of the Arnino silvoarable system.

Costs - Investment	Total costs (€ plot⁻¹)	Labour (h plot⁻¹)	Of which labour costs (€ plot⁻¹)
Plant material			
Poplar (<i>Populus canadensis robusta</i>)	355		
Oak (<i>Quercus robur</i>)	355		
Transport	450		
Tree establishment			
Excavation with auger for digging hole for planting seedlings. For planting poplar on cultivated ground, diameter 30 cm, depth 100 cm. Supply not included	378	unknown	unknown
Planting manually	753	11.42	468.60
Tree protection			
Game fence	20 000	unknown	unknown
Costs - Operational			
	Total costs (€ plot⁻¹ year⁻¹)	Labour (h plot⁻¹ year⁻¹)	Labour costs (€ plot⁻¹ year⁻¹)
Tree management			
Weed control	151	unknown	unknown
Watering trees	535	4.00	unknown
Pruning (annual maintenance)	592	21.67	unknown

Table 15. Detailed data on working operation for the Italian case-study.

Operation	Operation costs (labour included) (€ ha⁻¹)			Operation hour (h ha⁻¹)			Labour (€ ha⁻¹)		
	Sorghum		Vicia faba	Sorghum		Vicia faba	Sorghum		Vicia faba
	bicolor	durum		bicolor	durum		bicolor	durum	
Chisel ploughing - 30 cm	145.80	143.40	167.40	1.80	1.80	1.80	36.00	36.00	36.00
chisel disc	51.10	51.10	51.10	0.70	0.70	0.70	14.00	14.00	14.00
clod breakers	51.10	51.10	51.72	0.70	0.70	0.70	14.00	14.00	14.00
fertilization	62.21	59.33	44.23	0.50	0.50	0.50	10.00	10.00	10.00
grubber			48.30			0.70			14.00
harvesting	68.00	68.15	68.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	20.00	20.00	20.00
herbicide	48.72	67.54	52.27	0.50	0.50	0.50	10.00	10.00	10.00
hoeing	68.00			1.00			20.00		
ploughing - 30 cm		193.33	195.00		1.50	1.50		30.00	30.00
rotary harrowing	85.00	85.00	85.62	0.50	0.50	0.50	10.00	10.00	10.00
sowing	154.48	239.23	150.21	2.00	2.00	2.00	40.00	40.00	40.00
Spring-tooth harrowing	62.00			1.50			30.00		
stalk chopper	94.50	94.50	99.64	1.50	1.50	1.50	30.00	30.00	30.00
Sum	890.92	1052.68	1013.49	11.70	10.70	11.40	234.00	214.00	228.00

3.4.4 Results and discussion

3.4.4.1 Cost-benefit analysis

The cost-benefit analysis performed with INTACT evaluates the financial performance of establishing and managing poplar and oak trees on cropland, considering only the revenues and costs directly related to wood production. No comparison with alternative land uses or crop yield was included. Results were calculated considering a unit area of 3.28 ha (fields 21, 22, and 23; a small part of the case study), a simulation (analysis) period of 20 years and a discount rate of 4%. A summary of the cash flow lifetime of the poplar and oak trees is presented in Table 16. The model included establishment costs (year 0), annual maintenance costs, revenues from timber, and free cash flows as the net of revenues and costs from year 0-20.

3.4.4.2 Cash flow and revenue profile

Wood production starts from year 1 but growth rate is species-dependent. In this scenario, wood is sold in year 20. The free cash flow (FCF) is negative from year 0 until year 10, which is due to initial investment (€22290), and annual costs around €743 or less each year after that for maintenance. In total, the costs add up to €31882. The FCF becomes positive from year 20 as wood becomes a marketable product. Year 20 is the only year when there is a revenue. In INTACT's simulation timespan, total earnings from wood production reach €16607. The total benefits (revenue from timber) amount to €16 607. After all costs (€31 882) are paid, the poplar and oak trees leave a net cash return of around -€15 274. Even when adjusting for inflation and the time value of money, the investment still shows a negative return of -€22 244 over 20 years.

Table 16. Cash flow timeline of oak and poplar trees for the Arnino case (€). At the left, benefits and costs are both split into annual yield or costs, and cumulative yield or costs. Below, the free cash flow (FCF), discounted free cash flow (DFCF), discount rate, and cumulative free cash flow (CFCF) are shown.

Year	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Benefits											
Wood	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cumulative yield	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Costs											
Annual costs	22 290	1 278	1 278	743	743	743	743	743	743	743	743
Cumulative costs	22 290	23 568	24 847	25 589	26 332	27 075	27 818	28 561	29 304	30 046	30 789
FCF	- 22 290	- 1 278	- 1 278	- 743	- 743	- 743	- 743	- 743	- 743	- 743	- 743
DFCF	- 22 290	- 1 229	- 1 182	- 660	- 635	- 611	- 587	- 564	- 543	- 522	- 5023
Discount rate	0.04										
CFCF	- 22 290	- 23 519	- 24 701	- 25 361	- 25 996	- 26 607	- 27 194	- 27 758	- 28 301	- 28 823	- 29 325
Year	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	Total
Benefits											
Wood	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16 607	16 607
Cumulative yield	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16 607	
Costs											
Annual costs	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1 093	31 882
Cumulative costs	30 789	30 789	30 789	30 789	30 789	30 789	30 789	30 789	30 789	31 882	
FCF										15 514	- 15 275
DFCF										7 081	- 22 244
Discount rate	0.04										
CFCF	-29 325	-29 325	-29 325	-29 325	-29 325	-29 325	-29 325	-29 325	-29 325	-22 244	

The results from Table 16 are shown graphically in Figure 16, including the revenue from timber (green line), and the costs (red line). In this case, there is no break-even point as the costs incurred in year 0 are not covered by the revenue in year 20.

Figure 16. Cost-benefit analysis of the Italian case study.

Looking at the results from Table 17, we can see that the NPV is -€22244, using a discount rate of 4%. The IRR is -4%, and thereby below the 4% discount rate. The analysis considers an investment cost (excl. VAT and without subsidies) of €22290. Figure 16 showed that the payback period was not reached within the simulation time. Lastly, for the benefit: cost ratio, we look at the total benefits and costs. The revenue from wood amount to €16607, compared to total costs of €31882, resulting in a benefit-cost ratio of nearly 1:2. This value suggests that for every €2 invested, the trees only return €1 in benefits.

Table 17. The results of Italy's case study.

Financial metrics	Units	Value	Additional info
NPV	(€)	-€22 244	At a 4% discount rate
IRR	(%)	-4	Annual return
Investment cost (excl. VAT and without subsidy)	(€)	€22 290	One-time investment in Year 0
Payback period	(Years)	-	Based on cumulative free cash flow
Benefit: cost Ratio	/	1: 1.91	Benefits per €1 invested

The lack of profitability in this scenario can largely be explained by i) the cost of the expensive fence (€20,000) to protect the trees from game, and ii) the potential revenue from the oak trees occurs beyond the 20-year time period considered in the analysis. Poplar, a fast-growing tree species, can be harvested around 20 years which fits INTACT's simulation time. Harvesting oak before 20 years would not happen in reality. This implies that INTACT version 1 is not suitable for modelling slow-growing tree species with a simulation time of 20 years.

As mentioned earlier, the INTACT model includes only costs and revenues related to trees, excluding any other income such as crops. For this case study, the INTACT tool only modelled poplar and oak trees. Since the system at Arnino included oak trees, a slow-growing species, the target harvest period (over 40 years) extended beyond INTACT's 20-year simulation window. Because of the high fencing costs, the analysis indicated that the tree only system was unprofitable, as there are no crop yields to offset the substantial upfront investment costs. Showing this result to farmers might correctly or incorrectly discourage them to adopt tree planting or agroforestry. By contrast, the Farm-SAFE model showed a positive return from a tree-only system.

3.5 Feedback on the two tools in the Living lab

During the Living Lab activities that were held on 16-17 April 2025 in Pisa (Italy), the Farm-SAFE and INTACT financial tools were shown and tested with the participants (four farmers, four advisors, and four researchers were attending).

Farm-SAFE

A general introduction of Farm-SAFE was presented to the participants, the main features and the conceptual framework on which the model was built was explained. Some results were also shown; but due to the difficulties in using the model, Farm-SAFE was not directly tested by the participants. In general stakeholders were interested in Farm-SAFE and found the tool useful for predicting the cost and the potential benefits of agroforestry systems. They realize its usefulness as a support tool to provide a financial assessment when presenting loan requests to banks. Advisors were also happy with the potentiality of the tool.

The major drawbacks are the complexity of the tool, mainly due to the not-friendly user interface and large amount of data required. These main disadvantages dis-incentivise farmers from using this tool, which is still primarily a research tool.

INTACT

After a brief presentation and explanation of the tool, farmers were put in pairs with advisors and they were asked to imagine an agroforestry system, trying to simulate the costs of establishment. INTACT was used by the farmers and advisor with the support of a researcher.

Compared to Farm-SAFE, the Living Lab participants greatly appreciated the usefulness of INTACT and found it more user-friendly. However, they pointed out some weaknesses of the tool. The main drawback was the difficulty to use INTACT in Mediterranean conditions due to the unavailability of Mediterranean species such as olive trees. Additionally, they would appreciate the option of drawing their field at the beginning of the simulation (for example like the feature present in the tool CARAT), adapting the prices to regional conditions, and translating the tool into other languages such as Italian.

Once the Living Lab participants tested the tools, they were asked to fill out a grading form. A summary of the feedback provided is presented in Table 18 and Table 19 and the complete results are included in Appendix .

Table 18. Grades gives by Italian Living Lab participants to tested/demonstrated tools (including grading system). Grades go from 1 to 3 where 1 is the lowest and 3 is the highest.

Tool Stakeholder/User		Farm-SAFE		INTACT	
		Usability	Utility	Usability	Utility
1	Farmer	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0
2	Advisor	1.0	3.0	2.0	2.0
3	Advisor/Researcher	1.0	3.0	2.5	3.0
4	Farmer	1.0	1.0	2.0	3.0
5	Farmer	1.0	3.0	3.0	2.0
6	Advisor	1.0	2.0	2.0	1.0
7	Farmer	1.0	3.0	1.0	2.0
8	Advisor	1.0	2.0	3.0	2.0
Average		1.0	2.3	2.1	2.1

Table 19. Summary of a qualitative evaluation of Farm-SAFE and INTACT tools. Complete qualitative evaluation is displayed in Appendix

	Farm-SAFE	INTACT
Marks (1-5) (1: low; 5: high)	2.9	3.4
What would you improve about the tool?	Improve the usability	Adaptation of the tool to other regions (i.e. Mediterranean) and languages
Does the tool help you solve your problems? If no, what specific problems does it solve instead?	Overall useful but too complicated to be used by farmers	It provides help for the evaluation but if it is possible to adapt data and tree species for a specific region/country farmers are willing to use it
How would you improve the usability of the tool?	Improvement of user interface	Include the possibility to draw a map, and insert google maps location (i.e. like in CARAT); Translation to other languages

4 German case study

4.1 Background to case study and assumptions

The case study farm in Germany is the Domin Farm Peickwitz located in the LL Brandenburg (Germany), a small family-run farm with a comparatively small farming area. The farm extends over 370 ha, including 50 ha of grassland and 320 ha of arable land. Of this, 130 ha comprises restored mining areas. The farm also includes 50 ha of forest, 30 suckler cows, 30-40 fattening pigs, 200 poultry (geese and ducks), and approx. 50 laying hens (see: [D2.3](#) for more details).

As the first agroforestry system operation was implemented in March 2015, with an initial area of about 40 ha, this farm is considered to represent an ‘advanced’ case study. Tree species include alder (*Alnus* sp.), poplar (*Populus* sp.), willow (*Salix* sp.) and black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia*) planted in strips on a 30 ha field on the west of the farm that was at risk of erosion. In subsequent years agroforestry was extended and new systems added, employing more tree species, such as black alder (*Alnus glutinosa*), sweet chestnut (*Castanea sativa*), wild pear (*Pyrus pyraster*), field maple (*Acer campestre*) and tree hazel (*Corylus colurna*) as well as shrubs such as common rock pear (*Amelanchier rotundifolia*) and elderberry (*Sambucus nigra*).

The arable land of the case study farm is characterised by a comparatively low yield, expressed in a German-based yield factor of approx. 22 out of 100 points. This corresponds to the farming yield classification of area V (“Landbaugebiet V” – LBG V), which corresponds to the least productive zone.

Figure 17. Map of the Domin farm Peickwitz, with delineated subsystems of the agroforestry. (source: Google Earth)

For the financial analysis included in the present report, the oldest system will be analysed, comprising a silvoarable system with primarily short rotation poplar (Section A, Figure 17). Section A is comprised of the following woody components:

- A102: 9 rows of poplar; area = 0.68 ha; planting density = 2.7 x 1.0 m
- A104: 5 rows poplar; area = 0.42 ha; planting density = 2.7 x 0.5 m
- A105E: 5 rows poplar; area = 0.39 ha; planting density = 2.7 x 1.0 m
- A105W: 5 rows poplar; area = 0.39 ha; planting density = 2.7 x 0.5 m

The total area of the tree component of the silvoarable system stocked with poplar is approximately 1.9 ha, and the total area of the field is approximately 25 ha. Therefore, the ratio between arable crop and woody crop within the system currently used for the calculation scenario is 92% (arable crop) to 8% (woody crop). The additional 1.31 ha of black locust and 0.15 ha of a poplar-hardwood combi system that were planted in 2020 are also present in the field, but dismissed for simplicity of the calculations as they are planned for a different use than SRC; therefore in reality, the total share of wooded area is higher at present. The mean planting density of the poplars was 9,250 cuttings ha⁻¹. The crop rotation included in the calculations for the field crops is forage rye (year 1), oats (year 2), and winter rye (year 3).

4.2 Qualitative evaluation

4.2.1 Confirming the agroforestry innovation/system of interest

The first set of questions described the agroforestry system of interest.

- How much land have you used for the agroforestry system?
The first woody stripes with poplar and black locust were established in 2015. The summed-up area of the wooded part of this part of the agroforestry system is approximately 1.88 ha, and the total area of the field is approximately 25 ha. In 2016, first expansion with 2 rows of trees (approx. 1 ha) on permanent grassland, with strips of 25 m, with the aim of biomass production.
- Which tree species did you choose?
Initially, we started with an alley cropping system, primarily with hybrid poplar (Max III, Bakan, FW II, Vesten), and some black locust near the farm building, for energy use and poultry husbandry for Christmas- and St. Martin Geese, ducks and chicken. Tree species on the grassland are willow, poplar, and alder. A fruit tree system (apple, pear, elderberry, serviceberry) and the production of valuable timber (Turkish hazel, grey poplar, field maple, chestnut), partly in rows and partly on small batches/groups, completes the farm.
- Have they all grown well?
Yes, even in extreme drought years, like 2018, when the silage maize suffered from drought, the trees performed well. The initial planting of trees for the production of valuable wood suffered considerably from browsing by roe deer; full fencing, therefore, seems obligatory.
- Would you use the same tree species again?

Yes.

- What density did you plant them at? Do you think you will thin them during the rotation? If so, in which year?

For the fast-growing tree species, no thinning was necessary. Poplars were planted in lines with a distance of 2.7 m, usually with 5 lines per strip. With respect to the density within the rows, we tried with a distance of 1 m and 0.5 m, thus a density of 9,250 cuttings ha⁻¹ on average. In the past, double rows were common practice to plant in SRC in Germany, however, it was already shown that this pattern led to lower growth rates due to stronger competition between the trees. Furthermore, harvesting with a combine, especially in later years, has proven difficult. For stronger stem diameters, single-row harvesting became the method of choice. Timber producing trees will need thinning every few years. The fruit trees also need care in the first years.

- How did you manage the tree strip area? Do you still have to manage it in any particular way?

Manual weeding in the year of establishment was quite labour-intensive. Some special machinery, like a narrow cultivator, was custom-built so that together with a very small tractor, could handle the weeding in the narrow rows between the tree lines.

- What crops/livestock are you using in the rows between the trees? Do you think this will evolve over time as the trees grow bigger?

In the silvoarable system we grow, rye, oats, wheat, barley, teff, corn, sudan grass, proso millet, field grass, and alfalfa. The silvopastoral system, located on permanent grassland, is grazed during the summer season by a herd of suckler cows, including their offspring, and temporarily used as a chicken run. As trees grow, they are more robust towards browsing and provide better protection from the sun. The chicken system with a mobile chicken coop was discontinued, as the chicken became the prey of hawks and most probably foxes. Experiments with reflecting mirror balls did not mitigate the problem.

- Do you plan to plant more plots of agroforestry in the future? If so why/why not?

The system has evolved over the years and more elements have been added. Especially the fruit tree systems are still in their infancy, thus, we will now wait and watch how everything is developing.

- Would you do your agroforestry in the same way again if you knew what you know now?

Yes

4.2.2 Perceived advantages and disadvantages of the agroforestry system

A summary of benefits and disadvantages of agroforestry, as identified by the farmer, is shown in Table 20. The main reason for the establishment of the agroforestry was severe wind erosion in previous years. The topsoil was blown away due to its light characteristics in Brandenburg (termed “Sandbox”), even forming little dunes at the farm's fence. Therefore, a layout perpendicular to the main wind direction (westerly winds) was established.

As the annual electricity costs for the farm were ever-increasing to more than 25,000 € per year, resulting from an electricity requirement of 105,000 kWh y⁻¹, and electricity procurement costs of 0.24 €/kWh⁻¹. The electricity consumption is mainly due to the operation of the cooling system in the company's butchery and the shop, as well as the farm's consumption in the social buildings. The company's heat requirement is also substantial, with 350,000 kWh per year. This requires approximately 64 tonnes of wood per year, which is about 400 m³ of SRC. The biogas plant, which previously contributed to the energy bill, had to be closed down, as in years of low yields, fodder had to be purchased, making the entire biogas business unprofitable.

Table 20. Perceived benefits and disadvantages of a silvoarable system.

Benefits of system	Disadvantages of system
<i>Thanks to the good growth of the trees in difficult years with little to no yield in some of the crops, the wood chips can provide a substantial economic return after a few years.</i>	<i>A rather low price for wood chips after planting in 2015 to the end of 2021 was putting economic pressure on the decision, however, it changed with the doubling in energy prices after the invasion of Russia into Ukraine.</i>
<i>A positive reaction to media coverage of agroforestry at the farm boosted direct sales in the butchery and provided additional income from direct sales of wood chips, e.g. for ornamental purposes.</i>	<i>The extremely well-growing black locust (<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>) is no longer permitted for agroforestry in Germany. This species performs well in dry, continental conditions and its unwanted root propagation can easily be handled on arable land; however might be difficult in permanent grassland, where ploughing is prohibited.</i>
<i>Subsection of the large field created better conditions concerning micro-climate (less dry out effects from wind, less wind erosion)</i>	<i>The main direction of farming had to be changed, increasing the headland and slightly creating more detour efforts.</i>
<i>The presence of trees also benefited biodiversity substantially, with nesting birds, birds of prey, bats and farmland birds finding more insects.</i>	
<i>Substantial economic contribution through own use as fuel for heat and warm water production for the farm and its side businesses.</i>	

Additional questions on identifying the key opportunities and barriers to implementing the agroforestry system, and the financial questions to be addressed

- What have been the key challenges/barriers to establishing and managing your system? Were there any challenges associated with finding the trees, learning how to look after trees, managing the crops or animals between the trees, using machinery, etc.?
Lack of workforce: It is increasingly difficult to find good personnel for work on the farm.
Technical failure: One of the new explorations in the value chain included the set-up of four pyrolysis reactors to produce charcoal and biochar as a soil amendment. This did not

work out well. The handling and workflow have proven to be difficult; the process was hard to control. The promised integration of excess heat into the farm's energy supply concept did not work out. Currently, only two of the four reactors are still at the farm, but are hardly used.

- What particular opportunities and benefits do you think the outputs of your agroforestry system provide? Are you using the outputs to satisfy a need on the farm? Do you have a sales outlet for your tree products? Do you process and sell the products yourself? Do you have a restaurant, holiday let, or farm shop where you sell the products? etc.

The farm plays an active role in the dissemination of agroforestry practices in the region and beyond and the farmer was awarded to be an "Agroforestry Ambassador" by DeFAF. For the public, an educational trail with signposts, pictures and a barcode for additional information was set up. Regular events as the annual Farm Festival and hosting Brandenburg's Thanksgiving Event attracted many visitors. The farmer was also awarded the Professor Niklas-Medal in 2024, the highest award for farming in Germany, for his long-term engagement in agroforestry since 2015.

- What are the key technical/economic/management questions that keep you awake at night!

Answered above.

- How can our team help answer specific questions that you have regarding the management of your agroforestry?

The modelling shows the difficulties of conventional farming in times of climate change on the one side but also revealed the potential of trees in agroforestry systems with respect to economics.

- What are the key specific economic questions that you have regarding your agroforestry? Although the farmer did not specify a specific economic question, for the purposes of the deliverable, we completed a financial analysis of the system using the AgroForstRechner model.

4.3 Financial analysis

4.3.1 Modelling with AgroForstRechner

The financial evaluation with AgroForstRechner (AF-R) is based on a high number of input parameters which are then used to calculate economic values such as net present value (NPV) and annuity. An integrated database can be used for some input parameters, which provides the user with reference values. These serve as aid for improved estimation of individual parameters, but can also be included directly in the calculation as reference values.

Agroforestry still lacks empirical values for financial evaluations. This is one reason why some farmers are reluctant to establish agroforestry together with the long time period to derive a revenue compared to arable cropping. A financial comparison of agroforestry and mono-crop areas thus only makes sense if the total utilisation period is considered (KTBL, 2017). This, in turn, means that it can be inappropriate to use gross margins (i.e. revenues minus variable costs) as the standard means of comparison. Hence, the financial analysis needs to be implemented on the basis of a standardised area (€ ha^{-1}) and time reference ($\text{€ ha}^{-1} \text{ period}^{-1}$). It should also consider the time preference for money using a discount rate.

According to KTBL (2017), production processes with different production durations can be properly compared and evaluated in terms of their profitability using annuities. Annuities are determined using dynamic investment calculations, which, in contrast to static methods, consider the temporal occurrence of cash flows (Becker et al., 2014). Thus, all revenue generated is offset against the cost items, and the resulting profits and losses are discounted from the beginning (start of investment) using an imputed interest rate. This results in a net present value (NPV) for the individual years, which can be either positive or negative. Dynamic Investment Appraisal (DCF) is a common method for assessing land use systems that are characterised by high initial investments (Bemmann et al., 2007; Grünewald et al., 2009).

The NPV is defined as the sum of all costs and revenues that are incurred after a certain point in time and are discounted to this point in time. The annuity can be calculated from the capital values. This represents the theoretical amount that can be withdrawn as a constant annual profit contribution during the investment or utilisation period while maintaining the capital invested. In mathematical terms, the annuity is the product of the capital value and the annuity factor, which in turn, depends on the interest rate and the investment period (Böhm et al., 2013).

Comparing the annuity of a hectare of woody agroforestry component with that of cropland requires a considerable amount of time for a farmer, as common programmes used in practice, such as those used to document land management, do not have such functions. The calculation of annuities becomes particularly complex when different agroforestry areas and/or utilisation periods are to be considered and compared with each other. Since such economic assessments and evaluations are relevant for decision-making before the planting

of an agroforestry system, tools such as the AF-R model may be useful for such preliminary calculations. Such tools should be quick to run and transparent, using farm-specific data (Tranchina et al., 2024).

The Innovation Group AUFWERTEN, a group of researchers and practitioners, initiated the German Association for Agroforestry (DeFAF), who developed the AF-R and still maintains it today. The tool aims to provide consultants and farmers interested in agroforestry with easy-to-use software that allows them to carry out a rough financial analysis tailored to the farm as precisely as possible. The AF-R can be downloaded and used free of charge from DeFAF's website (www.defaf.de). The structure and functionality of the AF-R are summarised in the manual. The following section provides examples of calculations for the energy utilisation of a woody agroforestry system cultivated in short rotation based on real data from the Domin Farm Peickwitz in southern Brandenburg.

4.3.2 Database

To enable users of the AF-R to generate results quickly, default values have been pre-filled for the majority of parameters that can be used for the calculation. Alternatively, individual values can also be entered. The default values for arable crops were taken from a data collection carried out for the economic evaluation of agricultural production methods in the state of Brandenburg, Germany, widely used in practice (Hanff and Lau, 2016). The State Office for Rural Development, Agriculture and Land Consolidation of the State of Brandenburg (LELF), regularly updates this data collection. Furthermore, empirical data were used to calibrate these reference values. In agroforestry systems with stem wood production, harvesting costs can vary greatly depending on the layout and purpose of the area. The same applies to by-products.

Yields from woody crops depend not only on the choice of species and variety but also on the location (Zehlius-Eckert et al., 2013). Factors such as groundwater availability also play an important role. However, the agricultural yield index inadequately reflects these. Nevertheless, it was decided to also base the default values of yields for trees and shrubs on the arable figures, as the user often does not have the relevant data for an extended site assessment, and the input mask would also be too complex for a rough economic assessment. To avoid overestimation of yields, generally less favourable conditions were assumed, especially concerning groundwater availability. Yields assumed as a function of the number of acres can be found in Werwoll (2017) and are based on unpublished expert assessments. The procedure for linking arable field numbers with the expected yields of the individual woody species is based on Röhle et al. (2010). In the case of trees and shrubs, a distinction was only made between willow/poplar, black locust and "other" tree species due to a lack of empirical values. For a precise, site-specific yield estimate, an individual site assessment (particularly concerning the groundwater table) should be considered, possibly including measurements of biomass growth at comparable sites.

As agroforestry wood is a relatively “new” product for many farmers, for which new markets need to be created, the user of the AF-R may choose between the two options “sale of the woody product” (as wood chips or logs) and “in-house energy utilisation by the farm” (using a combined heat and power (CHP) plant). To calculate the financial efficiency of in-house energy utilisation of woodchips, variable internal data on energy consumption is first required to estimate the size of the plant required to cover demand. This data is the basis for the factors that are decisive for the calculation, such as the energy costs of the operation, investment and operating costs for the CHP plant, the size of the wooded area required and the yields to operate the CHP plant or for the desired degree of coverage for energy demand.

4.3.3 Data inputs

Values for market revenues, direct costs, and labour costs were selected according to the farmers’ suggestions collected in several consultations face-to-face on the farm and online. However, some values were taken from the internal database as default values (Table 21).

Table 21. Values for the calculation of the annuity for woody crops, including the data required for the sale of wood chips (values rounded).

Parameters	Unit	Value
Interest rate	(%)	4
Total running time	(years)	30
Rotation time	(years)	5
Rotations	(number)	6
Woody species	/	Poplar
Earnings enhancement factors (ESF)	/	No
Water content of woodchips on sale	(%)	35
Producer price for woodchips	(€ t ⁻¹)	123
Field setup using GPS	(€ ha ⁻¹)	75
Soil preparation	(€ ha ⁻¹)	250
Planting material costs (9,250 poplar cuttings/ha)	(€ ha ⁻¹)	1,665
Planting costs (9,250 cuttings/ha)	(€ ha ⁻¹)	1,165
Initial maintenance costs up to and including year 2	(€ ha ⁻¹)	520
Harvesting costs	(€ ha ⁻¹)	660
Option transport costs shredder (> 5 km)	/	No
Reconversion costs	(€ ha ⁻¹)	1050

The latest producer price for the woodchip sales of 123.37 € t⁻¹ included in Table 21 **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**, corresponds to the woodchip price data with a water content of 35% for the North-region of Germany including Brandenburg and the first quarter of 2025, collected by (CARMEN, 2025), (see Figure 18 for the prices over the last 17 years).

Figure 18. Development of the average price in € per tonne of woodchips in Germany (regions North and South) for different dryness qualities (20% and 35% water content) (own graph, data from CARMEN, 2025).

4.4 Results

With the above mentioned assumptions, AgroForstRechner calculated that the arable crop resulted in a mean annual margin of -64 € ha^{-1} across a rotation of 30 years (Figure 19). This is derived from a total undiscounted revenue over the period of $15,750 \text{ € ha}^{-1}$ and undiscounted costs of $17,666 \text{ € ha}^{-1}$. However, these figures need to be discounted.

By contrast, the revenue from woodchips was calculated to result in a revenue of $22,708 \text{ € ha}^{-1}$ over the time period of 30 years. With associated costs of $9,472 \text{ € ha}^{-1}$, this results in a profit of $13,236 \text{ € ha}^{-1}$. The production costs of one ton (“break-even-price”) of woodchips is 51 € t^{-1} . As the price of woodchips in the last couple of years has tended to be above 100 € t^{-1} due to high oil prices as a result of the Russian invasion to Ukraine in Feb. 2022, see Figure 18), the production of woodchips for energy substitution seems to be a feasible farm business.

When the risk assessment is performed by entering values for a distribution of the arable crop and the wood crop fraction, the annuity of the entire agroforestry systems can be calculated. A slightly higher workload of the farming practices was factored in (5 % is the default value).

For the silvoarable system comprising a ratio of 92 % arable to 8 % woody component, AgroForstRechner still calculated a negative annuity of -34 € ha⁻¹, and a negative NPV of -4,352 € ha⁻¹. To obtain a positive annuity for the agroforestry system, the share of the woody component could be increased to 17 %. The farmer planted more trees in the subsequent years after 2015, so that the share of woody plants has already increased.

Figure 19. Annuity curve in € ha⁻¹ for arable and woody crops as well as for an agroforestry system with various shares of arable-tree component.

As the management costs for the arable crops are quite high concerning the low yields and additional costs required, agroforestry system appears to be an economically advantageous option for this farm. Furthermore, the agroforestry strips can be expected to significantly stabilise yields of the arable crops, especially on low-yielding sites (wind protection and resulting reduction of transpiration and evaporation). At present, such effects, which may also have a direct influence on the economic performance, are not taken into account by the AgroForstRechner tool.

Overall, the cultivation of woody plants therefore represents a far more economical land utilisation option for this area than the cultivation of arable crops. When considering longer periods and energy utilisation, agroforestry use also becomes increasingly attractive.

The above analysis also ignores the effect of any subsidies or grants related to tree planting and management. In Germany, support for agroforestry is available through EcoScheme #3 “Maintaining Agroforestry”. Although it has not been used by the farmer, this grant may be useful especially if the price of woodchips decline. In 2025, there is a top-up of 200 € per hectare available to maintain agroforestry, and it is paid based on the share of wooded area. For 2026, an increase to 600 € is expected, as agreed amongst the agricultural ministers of the state conference. However, the legal text for its implementation has not been yet finalised by the German Ministry of Agriculture. An investment funding for agroforestry in Pillar II is available in four German states, but as matters stand, not in Brandenburg.

4.4.1 Reflections

The AgroForstRechner calculator offers a wide range of possible inputs and options necessary as a basic building block for a financial assessment of the land management of a farm involving a short rotation coppice system. Comparative data can be generated quickly, which can be used for a rough financial assessment. If necessary, these can be corrected in more detail without great effort. Overall, however, a few improvements could be implemented in the future, such as more default values for calculating storage costs or options for utilising surplus thermal energy, which would make it necessary to further develop the calculator in the future.

In this context, however, it should be kept in mind that too much detail in a tool can quickly overwhelm the user. More variables often do not lead to significantly higher accuracy. On the other hand, each additional generalisation of possible variables can also lead to additional inaccuracies. This balancing process was a major challenge in the development of the AgroForstRechner model.

5 Dutch case study

5.1 Case study and assumptions

The Dutch case study farm is “Tussen de Hagen” located in Stoutenburg, the Netherlands, an organic family-owned dairy farm that started diversifying its operations several years ago with agroforestry as one of the new practices. Two different types of agroforestry systems have been planted over: fodder hedges and silvopasture with fruit and nut trees.

The largest agroforestry plot covers 3 ha, with 120 walnut and chestnut trees planted in rows with 19 m spacing for easy machine passage (from here onwards referred as the “nut field”, Figure 20). Furthermore, 18 standard apple and pear trees were planted on a field of 0.3 ha (from here onwards referred as the “fruit field”, Figure 21). Also, 600 m² of fodder hedge was planted, consisting of willow, alder and hazel, and another 800 m of hedges acting as field boundaries, consisting of blackthorn, hawthorn and hornbeam, among others. Part of the fodder hedges is also actively managed (besides the casual browsing by the cows) and therefore this type of fodder hedge could also be classified as short rotation coppice (SRC). Another fodder hedge (mostly consisting of hornbeam) is very actively browsed by the cows and requires no further management.

Figure 20. Nut field of Dutch agroforestry system, covering an area of 3 ha.

Figure 21. Fruit field of Dutch agroforestry system, covering an area of 0.3 ha.

5.2 Qualitative evaluation

5.2.1 Confirming the agroforestry innovation/system of interest

During November 2024, the DigitAF financial tool working group visited the farm and discussed the perceived advantages and disadvantages of the agroforestry systems with the son of the family. In the future, he will be the main responsible person for the farm operations. The farmer indicated that he was looking for more data to make better informed choices regarding the possible expansion of silvopasture with nut trees (Figure 22) and a short rotation coppice hedge to provide bedding for livestock (Figure 23).

A silvopastoral system with walnuts

Scale of agroforestry system: one of the agroforestry systems on the farm is a walnut silvopastoral system (Figure 22). One question that the farmer had was whether it would be a good idea to invest in machinery and/or labour to facilitate a scale up of the walnut system. In particular, the farmer was comparing hiring labour for harvesting walnuts versus investing in machinery for harvesting walnuts. One assumption the farmer has, is that for an intensive manual labour system there is an ideal scale of operations, whereas for a machinery intensive system there is another ideal scale of operations. These are two scenarios that the farmer would like to see explored in a cost/benefit analysis. Summarised, the questions here were:

- *What is the right scale for my agroforestry system?*
- *At what scale of operations is hired labour or machine harvesting cost-efficient?*

Figure 22. A silvopastoral system with walnuts at Tussen de Hagen (Photograph: Paul Burgess)

Grass yields: the farmer also had a question regarding the future effect of the trees on the production and quality of the grass. Dairy is expected to remain the main source of income for the farm, and the quantity and quality of the grass is an important factor determining farm profitability. One argument is that, as the trees mature, they will start to compete with the grass for nutrients, light, and water. However, another argument is that under extreme dry conditions, shading might positively impact the fodder quantity and quality and improve animal welfare and thereby milk quantity and quality.

The detailed interactions between trees, grass yields and quality, and milk production and quality is beyond the capability of the models currently available within the DigitAF project. However some of the DigitAF models can start exploring how basic tree-grass and/or tree-cow interactions can be integrated into existing agroforestry models. Summarised, the questions here as:

- *How will grass production be affected by the trees as they reach the maturity stage?*
- *Will there be competition over light, water, and nutrients between the grass and the trees? How will grass quantity and quality be affected?*
- *What is the effect of heat stress on cows? How will milk quantity and quality be affected?*
- *What will be the financial impact of the trees on the dairy operations?*

Tree management: the farmer reported that establishing the trees in the silvopastoral system required considerable time, effort, and knowledge. Some agroforestry advisors argue that

tree care is required to get to the desired tree performance and health, whereas others might argue that minimal care is needed to obtain a sufficient harvest. Moving forward to the harvesting of nuts, one question was whether it is beneficial to remove unripe fruits of newly planted trees early in the year so the tree can optimally invest in vigour and growth. The underlying assumption is that relatively little tree care results in low harvests and vice versa. Summarised, the question here is:

- *When is it profitable to spend time on tree maintenance vs. just “keeping the tree alive”?*

Wood chips for bedding

The farmer is thinking of amending the agroforestry operations with short rotation coppice (SRC) for the production of wood chips to provide bedding for livestock (Figure 23). The SRC could also serve as a fodder hedge (and it will in practice) but the focus was on wood chip production. He has already identified a plot with ditches where trees could be planted in parallel to these ditches. The farmer still has questions regarding the financials of the operational upkeep of such a system (planting, maintaining, harvesting), as well as the expected outputs of the system (quantity and quality of the wood chips). Summarised, the questions here are:

- *How many meters of hedge do I need for sufficient woodchip production?*
- *How much and what type of organic materials are needed (with which C/N ratio) to achieve a good compost from the deep litter stable manure?*
- *What are the financials (costs and benefits) of the short rotation coppice (SRC) system?*

Figure 23. A short rotation coppice at Tussen de Hagen (Photograph: Paul Burgess)

Table 22 and Table 23 further list the perceived benefits and challenges/disadvantages of the silvopasture and fodder hedge/SRC system.

Table 22. Perceived benefits and challenges/disadvantages of the silvopastoral system with walnuts.

Benefits of system	Disadvantages of system
<i>Production of walnuts and timber and potential revenue</i>	<i>Costs of establishment and management (establishment success rate; should you include costs of clearing?)</i>
<i>Continued grass production and some shade for cattle (animal welfare)</i>	<i>Potential loss in grass yield</i>
<i>Benefits of pruning: clearance of machinery Creates a pleasant environment for customers; organic ethos/story</i>	<i>Costs of pruning; lower nut yields Value of walnuts and methods/costs of harvesting are unknown</i>

Table 23. Perceived benefits and challenges/disadvantages of the fodder hedge or short rotation coppice system.

Benefits of system	Challenges/Disadvantages of system
<i>Production of woodchip as bedding</i>	<i>Need to dry wood</i>
<i>Reduced straw use and costs</i>	<i>Still need to buy some straw (to maintain C:N ratio)</i>
<i>On-farm production of bedding</i>	<i>Cost of hedge system</i>
<i>Use as fodder hedge – perceived medicinal benefits</i>	<i>Loss of land which was in grass production</i>
<i>Wind protection on farm; biodiversity gain; landscape benefits</i>	<i>Uncertainties on quality of woodchip (wet chip can create health problems)</i>

5.3 Financial analysis

Many questions came up in conversation with the farmer. Three digital tools seemed suited for (partially) answering some of the farmers' questions and/or provided a good question to test, evaluate, and improve the capacity and functioning of the tools. As such the two goals were: 1) answering the farmer's questions as well as possible, and 2) evaluating and improving the digital tools on the basis of real-life questions from a farmer.

5.3.1 Farm-SAFE modelling

Farm-SAFE seemed like a suitable digital tool to attempt to answer questions regarding the scale for walnuts, the trade-offs between trees and grass and milk production, and the level of tree maintenance. Although Farm-SAFE v3 does not have an animal component integrated into the model, there was interest in seeing if the modelling the tree-grass and tree-cow interactions could be developed because of its pertinence to grassland use in the Netherlands.

For the agroforestry system at Tussen de Hagen, the financial modelling in Farm-SAFE used data from the literature and from conversations with the farm manager and project team to identify the costs and benefits of production for a walnut/pasture system. The predictions from this modelling were then compared to the costs and benefits associated with a pasture only system which acted as a counterfactual. A time horizon of 30 years was assumed for the modelling, although it should be noted, that walnuts can be productive for longer than this

5.3.1.1 Livestock system prices and costs

The area and the number of cows on the farm, and the sources of revenue are shown in Table 24. For the pasture only system, the pasture yield was assumed to be 10 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, which appears to be a reasonable assumption based on data for the Netherlands (Schils et al., 2020). Whilst the grass produced on farm provided the majority of the livestock feed requirements (Table 29), this was supplemented by concentrates, bought in grass, silage, and fodder beet.

Table 24. Description of the dairy herd and sources of revenue at Tussen de Hagen.

Area of farm (ha)	72	Revenue	
Herd numbers		Milk	
Cows	100	Milk sales (l/cow)	8,200
Calves (0-1 year)	15	Milk value (€/litre)	0.58
Calves (1-2 year)	15	Cull cows	
Animals sold for meat	14	Sold to traders:	
Animals died	1	Mean meat weight of animals sold to trader (kg)	340
		Value of the animal sold to trader (€/kg)	4.50
		Number of animals sold to trader (n)	10
		Value per head (€/kg)	1,530
		Sales per cow (%)	10%
		Sold on farm:	
		Mean meat weight of animals sold from farm (kg)	340
		Value of animal sold on from farm (€/kg)	10
		Number of animals sold on from farm (n)	4
		Value per head (€/head)	3,400
		Sales per cow (%)	4%
		Subsidies	
		Single farm payment (€/ha)	335
		Other subsidies (€/ha)	

For the purposes of the modelling, it was assumed that the farm had 100 dairy cows, grazing on 72 hectares of land. The herd comprised in a number of young calves, and the number of calves reaching two years of age so that they could start producing (15) was balanced by the number of cows that were sold out of the herd (14) and natural mortality (1) (Table 24). Milk sales were assumed to be 8,200 l per year and each meat weight of each animal that was culled was assumed to be 340 kg, with the value assumed to be much greater for meat sold on farm than on to traders (Table 23). No replacement heifers were assumed to be needed and a single farm payment of €335 ha⁻¹ was assumed. Variable costs included those for the

production of grass, silage, hay, concentrates, fodder beet, bedding, veterinary costs and medicines, dairy robot, butchering costs, and other associated costs. Fixed costs included those for labour, fuel, electricity, water, and gas (Table 25).

Table 25. Variable and assignable fixed costs at Tussen de Hagen.

		Quantity produced or purchased for farm (t)	Quantity per cow (t cow ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	Cost (€ t ⁻¹)
Feed	Forage	401.5	4.015	40
	Purchased silage	190.0	1.9	250
	Hay	32.0	0.32	250
	Concentrates	178.0	1.78	630
	Fodder beets	100.0	1.0	85
	Milk	10.5	0.105	400
Bedding	Rapeseed straw	11	0.11	230
	Miscanthus straw	8	0.08	150
	Cereal straw	85	0.85	160
Other variable costs	Vets and medicines	Vets and med cost (€/farm)		7,515
		Artificial insemination cost (€/farm)		2,430
		Recording and registration cost (€/farm)		3,690
	Other livestock costs	Dairy robot lease (€/farm)		16,115
		Dairy robot consumables (€/farm)		24,385
		Butcher cost per kg of meat (€/kg)		2.50
		Amount of meat sent to butcher (kg)		1,360
		Cost of butchering (€/farm)		3,400
	Other costs (€/farm)		11,340	
Assignable Fixed costs	Labour	Labour time (h/y)		6,214
		Labour rate (€/h)		10.0
		Contractor cost (€/farm)		42,750
	Field machinery	Machinery cost (€/farm)		24,564
		Fuel	Quantity of fuel (litres/y)	
	Fuel price (€/litre)			1.60
	Electricity	Electricity consumption (kwh)		48,950
		Electricity rate (€/kWh)		0.16
	Water	Water cost (€/farm)		616
	Gas	Gas cost (€)		1,602

5.3.1.2 Agroforestry system yields, prices and costs

Grass component: the grass was assumed to occupy approximately 95% of the total area of the agroforestry system, given that the tree strips (fenced off to protect the trees), were spaced at 19 m row intervals, and being 1 m wide, occupied approximately 5% of the total area. In order to estimate the yield of grass under the trees, we used the outputs of the Yield-SAFE biophysical model which has previously been used to predict interactions between walnut (50 trees ha⁻¹) intercropped with fodder maize and wheat at Bentelo in the Netherlands (Graves et al., 2007). Given that the tree density being modelled for the walnut silvopasture system in Tussen de Haagen was 54 trees ha⁻¹, it was assumed that the data from Bentelo would be sufficiently close as a guide to the effect of the trees on the pasture over time.

The results suggest that pasture yields in the walnut silvopasture system, as a proportion of the yields in the pasture only system, would initially be relatively close to the sole crop yields but would decrease to about 40% of the pasture only yields by about year 30 due to competition for light and water from the walnut trees (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Predicted understorey crop yields (per cropped area) modelled for wheat and fodder maize under walnut using the Yield-SAFE model in the Bentelo area of the Netherlands, and the manual interpolation used to obtain the pasture yields under walnut.

Tree component: since no model for walnut nut production exists within Yield-SAFE, yields from the RekenTool (version 4.0) for walnut (*Juglans regia*) were used. This showed that yields were low, essentially 0 t ha⁻¹, in the first 5 years, but increased from about 1 kg tree⁻¹ in year 6 to 15 kg tree⁻¹ in year 14 and 28 kg tree⁻¹ in year 16-20. It was assumed that the trees would yield at this rate until year 30, the final year of the time horizon for this simulation (Figure 25). For the financial analysis, the per tree yield data was expressed on a per hectare basis using the planting density of the orchard (54 trees ha⁻¹) (Figure 25).

Figure 25. Walnut yield profile expressed a) per tree and b) per hectare for walnut trees (*Juglans regia*) taken from RekenTool (version 4).

The value of the main revenue sources of the walnut trees is shown in Table 26. The data are compiled from a variety of sources. Subsidies were calculated based on 50% of the cost of the establishing the trees for the first two years. It was assumed that the single farm payment

would be marginally reduced due to the reduction of pasture land taken by the trees and tree strip. The walnuts were valued at €5,500 t⁻¹ (Rekentool, version 4), and firewood, assumed derived from tree pruning, tree shaping, and eventual tree removal, at €73.7 m⁻³ based on data from oak, beech, alder, and birch firewood sales on the Dutch FLAGMA website (FLAGMA, 2025). Since the FLAGMA website provides firewood values in per tonne units, the per tonne value of firewood (€110 t⁻¹) was converted to cubic metre values (€73.7 m⁻³) using the volumetric density of walnut from the Engineering Toolbox Website (Density of Wood Species: Data & Material Guide). This was given as a range from 640–700 kg m⁻³, so the average value (670 kg m⁻³) was used to convert the firewood value from tonnes to cubic metres in order to derive the units needed for the Farm-SAFE model. In the Netherlands, the subsidy for planting trees is given as a proportion of the cost of establishment in the first two years. This was calculated automatically by the Farm-SAFE model, based on the establishment costs defined in Table 27.

Table 26. Assumed revenue sources for the silvopasture system in the Netherlands

Source of revenue	Assumptions
Subsidies	Calculated, based on 50% of tree planting cost for the first two years of the rotation
Walnut value	(€ t ⁻¹) 5,500
Firewood value	(€ m ⁻³) 73.7

The walnuts were planted in 2020, and costs included establishment costs such as the cost of the walnut plants, individual tree protection, labour for ground preparation and weeding, labour for marking out, irrigation, and labour. After the establishment year, costs included a variety of maintenance costs for the trees, including weeding costs, pruning costs, epicormic removal costs, walnut harvesting costs and tree clearing costs. Most of these were derived during discussion with the farmer or from data in the literature and from project partners. However, walnut harvesting costs, assuming hand harvesting, were taken from a publication by Jones et al. (1998) who document the costs and labour rates associated with hand harvesting of black walnut trees in an agroforestry system in Missouri, USA (Harper, 1998).

Table 27. Input table of costs assumed for the walnut trees in the silvopasture system in the Netherlands.

Input category	Inputs	Units	Walnut costs
Establishment year		(y)	2020
Assumed rotation		(y)	30
Tree density		(tree ha ⁻¹)	54
Establishment costs	Cost of plant	(€ tree ⁻¹)	90.00
	Cost of individual tree protection	(€ tree ⁻¹)	6.37
	Labour for ground preparation and weeding	(hr ha ⁻¹)	1.1
	Labour for marking out	(hr ha ⁻¹)	5
	Labour for planting trees	(min tree ⁻¹)	15
	Labour for tree protection	(min tree ⁻¹)	6.5
	Irrigation investment	(€ ha ⁻¹)	442.86
	Irrigation costs	(€ yr ⁻¹)	-
	Labour for irrigation	(h ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	-
	Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30
Weeding costs	Year of first weeding	(year)	2020
	Annual labour for weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)	27
	Annual cost of weeding	(€ tree ⁻¹)	2.16
	Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30
Epicormic costs	Year of first removal of epicormics	(year)	1
	Year of first removal of epicormics	(year)	30
	Labour for removal of epicormics	(min tree ⁻¹)	0.5
	Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30
Pruning costs	Year of first prune	(year)	1
	Minutes per tree at first prune	(min tree ⁻¹)	15
	Height at first prune	(m)	1
	Minutes per tree at last prune	(min tree ⁻¹)	45
	Height at first prune	(m)	6
	Removal of prunings	(min tree ⁻¹)	0
	Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30
Harvesting costs	Labour per tonne walnuts	(hr t ⁻¹)	35.3
	Cost of labour	(€ hr ⁻¹)	30
Clearing costs	Labour	(min tree ⁻¹)	60
	Removal of tree	(min tree ⁻¹)	120
	Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30

5.4 Results

5.4.1 Rotation and yield of arable and silvopasture systems

The grass in the pure pasture system was assumed to provide an average yield of around 10 t ha⁻¹ (dry matter). Data from the Netherlands between 1900 and 2020 (Schils et al., 2020) suggest that this is reasonable assumption on a Netherlands wide scale, although farm, regional, and annual variation would be expected.

Figure 26. Assumed dry matter grass yield (t ha⁻¹) for the pasture system in the Netherlands case study (Based on Schils et al., 2020).

Due to lack of data, the pasture in the agroforestry system was interpolated based on yields modelled for fodder maize and wheat during the SAFE project. Based on this assumption, yields declined from 10 t ha⁻¹ in year 1 of the rotation to approximately 4 t ha⁻¹ in year 30 of the rotation due to the effect of tree growth on the grass (Figure 27).

Figure 27. Assumed dry matter grass yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$) for the silvopasture system in the Netherlands case study based on previous modelling undertaken on the SAFE project (see Figure 24).

The assumed yield profile of the walnuts is shown in Figure 28.

Figure 28. Walnut yield profile for walnut trees planted at a density of $53\ trees\ ha^{-1}$, based on the yield profile for individual walnut trees (*Juglans regia*) in the Rekentool (version 4) model.

5.4.2 Grassland and silvopasture undiscounted revenue and costs

The grass yield is a major determinant of the pattern of revenue and costs in the livestock system. In the pasture only system, given that the yields were assumed to be constant, the calculated revenue and costs were also constant (Figure 29).

Figure 29. Pattern of costs and revenue over a 30 year rotation in the pasture only system for the Netherlands case study.

In the silvopasture system, the pattern of revenue and costs was not constant (Figure 30). The pattern of revenue showed that annual income increased as the trees grew and produced more walnuts.

Figure 30. Pattern of grant and non-grant revenue and costs over a 30 year in the silvopasture system for the Netherlands case study.

The level of non-grant revenue from the silvopasture system was derived from the sum of the income from feeding the grass to the cows and the value of the walnut harvests, and the timber from clear-felling in year 30 (Figure 31).

Figure 31. Pattern of revenue (€ ha⁻¹) from the livestock component and the tree component of the silvopasture system in the Netherlands (Is this revenue or margin?)

5.4.3 Grassland and silvopasture discounted and undiscounted net revenue

The undiscounted (discount rate = 0%) cumulative net margin predicted a higher cumulative net present value for the silvopasture compared to the grassland system (Figure 32). However, due to the initial establishment costs, the silvopasture system returned a negative cumulative net margin for the first six years of the rotation, only becoming profitable after year 16. The pasture system provided a positive return from the first year and was never in deficit during any year of the rotation. Discounting the cumulative net margin (discount rate 4%) had little effect on the general patterns drawn from the analysis (Figure 33).

Figure 32. Undiscounted cumulative cash flow for the pasture only and silvopasture system at the Netherlands case study.

Figure 33. Discounted (discount rate = 4%) cumulative cash flow for the pasture only and silvopasture system at the Netherlands case study.

5.4.4 Pattern of arable and silvopasture labour use

The requirement for labour for looking after the dairy herd linked to the pasture system was the approximately 86 hr ha⁻¹ and was calculated not to vary year on year as input requirements for the pasture only system was assumed to be in a steady state as long as grass yields remained constant (Figure 34).

Figure 34. Labour requirement for the pasture only system at the Netherlands case study.

By contrast, the labour use in the silvopasture systems was substantially greater than the pasture only system on a per hectare basis (Figure 35). The modelling assumed that the labour requirement associated with the grass area was linked to the grass yield; hence it was assumed that the number of cows would decline. The labour associated with tree establishment and management was high for establishment, then decreased, in years 2 and 3, but then increased with additional tree pruning and shaping and as the trees became

larger. The labour for walnut harvesting was zero in the first five years due to the absence of walnut production, but increased thereafter to approximately 50 hr ha⁻¹ by the final years.

Figure 35. Labour requirement for the silvopasture system at the Netherlands case study.

The total additional labour required for the silvopasture system relative to the pasture system on a per hectare basis was generally between 20 and 70 hr ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, and this increased as the trees became larger and more productive, peaking in the clear felling year with an additional labour requirement of 188 hr ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Figure 36).

Figure 36. Additional time needed to manage the silvopasture system relative to the pasture system at the Netherlands case study.

5.4.5 Summary of the analysis using Farm-SAFE

The tabular summary in Farm-SAFE (Table 28) shows key results for the pasture only and silvopasture system (€ ha⁻¹) in terms of the overall undiscounted and discounted net present value (NPV), product revenue, grant revenue, and costs for a 30-year time horizon.

Table 28. Undiscounted, and discounted and equivalent annual values (EAVs) (discount rate = 4%) for the pasture and the components of the silvopasture system over a 30 year rotation.

		Pasture only system	Silvopasture system		
			Pasture component	Tree component	Combined
Undiscounted NPV	€ ha ⁻¹	42,137	31,740	72,554	104,294
Undisc. product revenue	€ ha ⁻¹	211,165	142,725	156,570	299,295
Undisc. grant revenue	€ ha ⁻¹	10,058	10,058	3,848	13,906
Undiscounted costs	€ ha ⁻¹	179,086	121,043	87,864	208,907
Discounted NPV	€ ha ⁻¹	25,259	20,333	28,631	48,964
Disc. product revenue	€ ha ⁻¹	126,584	94,157	72,989	167,146
Disc. grant revenue	€ ha ⁻¹	6,030	6,030	3,831	9,861
Discounted costs	€ ha ⁻¹	107,355	79,853	48,190	128,043
EAV of NPV	€ ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	1,461	1,176	1,656	2,832
EAV of product revenue	€ ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	7,320	5,445	4,221	9,666
EAV of grant revenue	€ ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	349	349	222	570
EAV of costs	€ ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	6,208	4,618	2,787	7,405

The discounted NPV shows that the combined income from the silvopasture system (48,964 € ha⁻¹) after 30 years was substantially greater the income for the pasture only system (25,259 € ha⁻¹). This was largely due to the projected income from the walnuts (28,631 € ha⁻¹), although grass production continued providing a substantial benefit to the farmer and over 30 years (20,333 € ha⁻¹). On an equivalent annual value basis, these results were equivalent to an annual income of 1,461 € ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ for the pasture only system and 2,832 € ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ for the silvopasture system, with the pasture component contributing 1, 176€ ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ and the tree component contributing 1,656 € ha⁻¹ a⁻¹ to the combined silvoarable system.

5.4.6 Practical reflections from modelling the Netherlands case study

The Farm-SAFE model was originally designed for silvoarable systems comprising timber trees and crops. Because the agroforestry system at Tussen den Haagen is composed of walnut trees and livestock, we found it challenging to model these systems in the Farm-SAFE model and had to implement some changes in the original model and adapt it to the case study. These challenges and changes are summarised here:

- Farm-SAFE was designed to model forestry species, and it was challenging to incorporate nut tree costs. Some modifications were made, but additional costs such as harvesting machinery and labour costs could be itemised. In our calculations, we assumed that harvesting was completed by a contractor.
- We could only incorporate one nut tree species at a time in the system. The system in the Netherlands includes a number of nut trees in the same plot. However, whilst modelling more trees together is interesting, it is worth noting that this would also require additional data and complexity in the model. A key challenge is considering how trees would affect

each other in a mixed system and how tree growth and yield would be affected in the long-term. To our knowledge, no temperate agroforestry growth models currently do this.

- The original model did not account for water irrigation costs at the establishment phase of the tree component of the silvoarable system; the model was adapted accordingly to include these costs.
- The model was originally developed for modelling silvoarable economics and does not currently include an easy way of modelling livestock systems, although livestock data can be added to the model. However this process was not intuitive, and it requires a high level of experience with the model.
- Given the complexity that can be added when incorporating additional modelling options within Farm-SAFE, it may be useful to develop specific versions of Farm-SAFE for specific purposes.

5.5 Modelling short rotation coppice using Final-ALS

The second agroforestry system considered for the Tussen de Hagen farm case study in the Netherlands was a short rotation coppice (SRC) hedge. For this purpose, a silvopastoral agroforestry system was proposed by the farmer with narrow strips/belts of fast-growing trees planted around his pasture land. As a model of this, the financial working group observed an existing hedge around a field with 2-3 rows of willows (*Salix alba*, *Salix x rubens*), which are approximately 6 m wide. The trees were about 5-7 m tall (Figure 23; Figure 37). The research question was to compare three scenarios comprising one, two, or three rows of trees in a SRC tree strip “coppice tree belt”. The length of the planted hedge was assumed to be 1020 m, being the combined length of two sides of three ditches each of 170 m length already existing in one of the farmers’ fields.

To examine the financial viability of the SRC, we used the “Final ALS” model. The first step was to derive an estimate of the biomass production of the short-rotation coppice for woodchips (energy biomass). This was based on models originally developed for selected growing zones in the Czech Republic. It is assumed that the trees are coppiced every 3-6 years with standard harvesting machinery (Figure 37). The original plan was to extend the analysis to include an assessment of revenue and costs, but this was not possible before the end of June 2025. The assumed arable system was considered to be a four-year crop rotation, comprising winter barley, winter wheat, rapeseed and maize. For this analysis, we used data from Czech Republic and the Final ALS model.

Figure 37. Existing hedges around fields with fast-growing trees at Dutch farm Tussen de Hagen; left), and possible harvesting technology of hedges/coppiced tree belts - New Holland mower-chipper (Michovsky experimental field, Czech Republic).

5.5.1 Production and yield assessment

Agroforestry systems with coppiced tree belts can be established and cultivated in a number of variants — according to the conditions of the location and needs of the farmer. For our task and also with the goal of optimising environmental and financial benefits, we assumed a 5.5 m-wide coppice tree belt with three rows of tree varieties/clones suitable for coppicing and biomass production e.g. poplars Max-4, 'AF2', 'Skado', willows 'Rokyta', 'Tora' and many other.

The Final-ALS model was used to predict the biomass yields from a 100 m length of a coppiced tree row. The model includes yield curves of biomass for poplar-willow SRC in different stand conditions of Czech Republic which has 5 growing zones (Vávrová et al., 2017; Weger et al., 2024). For the Tussen the Hagen Farm, the Czech team selected yield curves 4, 5, and 6 (expected yields of 10-14 t DM ha⁻¹ year⁻¹), because we consider that soil and climate conditions are very suitable for both poplar and willow at the farm.

Figure 38. Predicted woodchip (0-30 years) yields curves (derived from the Czech Republic) from short rotation coppice on a three year cropping cycle assuming a) a single 100 m row and b) a double 100 m row.

The assumptions within the model included:

- Standard planting scheme of trees in the coppice tree belt is 2 m x 0.5 m (x 1-3 rows).
- Production time is 22-30 years (22 years used in the calculation).
- We have collected yields of coppiced trees from existing “narrow” SRC plantations as well as newly established coppice tree belts to estimate positive edge effects on coppiced tree belts.

In our simulation, the total area of the coppiced tree belts would cover from 6 to 16% of the available area of field, if three edges of the field were planted with CTB, depending on the number of rows (e.g. 2-5.5 m wide x 300 m long). The predicted yields are shown in Table 29.

Table 29. Expected yields of woodchips from 100 m long coppice tree belts, coppiced/harvested in 3-year rotation with following parameters.

System	Proportion of a 1 ha field comprising a coppice tree belt	Coppice tree row design (meters)	Yield of woodchips (average triennial harvest)
Single row	6% (600 m ² / 1 ha)	2 m (2 m x 0.5 m)	5.5-7.5 m ³
Double row	12% (1200 m ² / 1 ha)	4 m (2 + 2 x 0.5 m)	10.5-15 m ³
Triple row	16% (1600 m ² / 1 ha)	5.5 m (2+2+1.5 x 0.5m)	14.5-20 m ³

The mean woodchip density was assumed to be about 0,28 t m⁻³ of fresh woodchips (48% moisture content, 2-3 weeks after winter harvest).

6 Finnish case study

6.1 Description of agroforestry on the case study farm

The selected farm in Finland is Kilpiän Tila, a 75 ha arable organic farm focused on cereal production in the region of Uusimaa, southern Finland. The reason for introducing agroforestry, hedges and a fruit tree orchard, was to reduce wind and water erosion, as a large proportion of the fields is situated on a rather steep slope. Both windbreaks (Figure 39) slow down the wind speed from the surrounding large open fields in the south. The fruit tree orchard was planted in contour lines on a slope to prevent erosion. Windbreak 3 was planted to create a physical barrier to prevent the spread of herbicides from a neighbouring farm (Figure 39).

Over recent decades the farm was under intensive cultivation and when the current owners took over, the soils at the farm were rather degraded. The new owners wanted to restore soil health and implement more environmentally friendly farming practices. Currently, about 25 ha are under agroforestry comprising 24 ha under cereal cultivation and a 1 ha fruit tree orchard.

Figure 39. Map showing a 25 ha section of the Finnish case study farm covering the agroforestry areas.

Fruit tree orchard: one hectare orchard composed of apples (300 trees), pears (200 trees), walnut (50 trees), and hazelnut (30 trees), positioned along contour lines (to prevent erosion). Between the trees in the alleys there is grass which is mowed but not harvested. Between the trees in the rows there are different berry bushes which are still very young and harvested by

hand, Siberian pea shrub (not harvested) and nuts (hazelnut and walnut, still too young to produce a crop).

There are also three windbreaks on the farm. **Windbreak 1** is 2 m wide and 391 m long, and composed of willow (planting distance every 50 cm)(area 0.11 ha) and black alder *Alnus glutinosa* (planting distance every 5 m). Willow is for basket making and alder is for timber production for furniture making in the future. Winter rye and spring crops are sown under the trees in a four-year rotation. Year 1: rye, undersown with green manure mixture (nitrogen fixers and grasses); year 2 comprised green manure ley; year 3 was spring crop (spelt, oats or pea) late cultivation and sowing of winter rye, and in year 4 the rotation returns to year 1.). In the centre part of the windbreak also some walnut and hazelnut seedlings are planted. **Windbreak 2a and 2b** are two windbreaks in V shape (length windbreak 2a: 238 m, length windbreak 2b: 348 m) planted with sea-buckthorn *Hippophae rhamnoides* (200 plants). **Windbreak 3** is a 60 m long windbreak in the south-east corner of the field planted with Siberian larch (30 plants), birch (30 plants) and hazel (30 plants). This windbreak was established to create a physical barrier to prevent the spread of herbicides from the neighbouring field.

6.2 Qualitative evaluation

Prior to completing a financial analysis, the farmer was asked to describe the main characteristics of the system.

- How much land have you used for the agroforestry system?
25 ha.
- Which tree species did you choose? Have they all grown well? Would you use the same tree species again?
Apple, pear, sea-buckthorn, hazelnut, walnut, willow, alder, birch, Siberian larch. They have grown well. Yes, to all. Willows and birch should not be planted close to tile drains because the roots will block the tile drains.
- What density did you plant them at? Do you think you will thin them during the rotation? If so, in which year?
Different densities for different species. Alder and birch will need thinning in about 30 years.
- How did you manage the tree strip area? Do you still have to manage it in any particular way?
Fruit trees are pruned and need weeding. Windbreak: willow and alder are sometimes harvested and also need some weeding.
- What crops/livestock are you using in the rows between the trees? Do you think this will evolve over time as the trees grow bigger?
Fruit tree orchard: Grass
Large field near the windbreak: Winter rye and spring crops are sown under the trees in a four-year rotation. Year 1: rye, undersown with green manure mixture (nitrogen fixers and

grasses); year 2 comprised green manure ley; year 3 was spring crop (spelt, oats or pea) late cultivation and sowing of winter rye, and in year 4 the rotation returns to year 1.

- Do you plan to plant more plots of agroforestry in the future? If so why/why not?
Not in the near future. The farmers are happy with the system. They could convert more areas into agroforestry, but they now have a viable farm and it would take a lot of time and effort to convert a more areas and they do not have time to invest in it, and they don't have customers for the tree crop.
- Would you do your agroforestry in the same way again if you knew what you know now?
No willows near tile drains. You have to keep 10 -15 m distance otherwise they will block the drains. The farmers would also do a double row of willow instead of a single row, to be able to cut down one row and still maintain the windbreak effect. The farmers would do the groundwork of the orchard differently and irrigate the trees from their seedling stage.

The farmer was then asked to quantify the main perceived benefits and disadvantages of the system with the walnuts orchard on grassland system. The main benefits were related to improving soil health. An observed disadvantage was that the farm was unable to process produce on the farm (Table 30).

Table 30. The farmer's perception of the benefits and disadvantages of the walnuts in grassland system.

Benefits of system	Disadvantages of system
<p><i>Before changing to agroecological methods, the soil was degraded and contained almost no organic matter. A shift to agroecological methods has clearly improved farm sustainability and the overall condition of the fields.</i></p> <p><i>The system is more resilient, e.g. to drought damage and wind erosion</i></p> <p><i>Economy: The farm is economically viable. The farm has low production costs and little external inputs</i></p> <p><i>Supply of inputs is fine. The farmers have good connections with suppliers (e.g. machinery, seeds) and a maintenance network.</i></p> <p><i>Good relations with customers</i></p>	<p><i>No on-farm processing: The farm is mainly selling raw materials without any further processing. For example, there is no grain processing. A higher added value could be generated by improving on-farm processing. In addition, the farmers have no time for hiring more personnel to help with and improve on-farm processing.</i></p>

The next set of questions related to the opportunities and barriers to implementing the agroforestry system.

- What have been the key challenges/barriers to establishing and managing your system? Were there any challenges associated with finding the trees, learning how to look after trees, managing the crops or animals between the trees, using machinery

Lack of marketing skills: The farmers feel they lack the necessary marketing skills for selling their products. In addition, they also lack the time to improve the marketing and their marketing skills.

Lack of time: The farmers have no time for hiring more personnel to help with and improve on-farm processing.

- What particular opportunities and benefits do you think the outputs of your agroforestry system provide? Are you using the outputs to satisfy a need on the farm? Do you have a sales outlet for your tree products? Do you process and sell the products yourself? Do you have a restaurant, holiday let, or farm shop where you sell the products? etc.

The cereals are bought by an industrial buyer and a local small-scale buyer. Fruits are sold directly on the farm. The willows are bought by an artisan basket producer. The timber from the forest is bought by the wood-processing industry. The mushrooms are bought by a mushroom buyer.

There would be opportunities for direct marketing: Direct marketing of grain or via a cooperative would be an interesting opportunity.

There would also be an opportunity for seedling production by establishing a tree seedling nursery. Tree seedlings could include species which are currently not very well available, for example walnut and hazel seedlings.

Advisory services: The farmers are currently already offering advisory services but there would be a large opportunity to develop these further, for example by offering courses for farmers.

Currently there are no advisory services available for starting new agroforestry systems. Farmers are interested in agroforestry but there are no advisors who can help with this. The interviewed farmer would have this knowledge and there would be a great opportunity to develop more advisory services.

The final set of questions related to the farmer's main technical, economic, or management questions.

- What technical/economic/management questions keep you awake at night!
Who is going to eat the apples? How do I store them? Will the deer eat the Siberian pea, sea-buckthorn and hazelnut shrubs in winter time?
- How can our team help answer specific questions that you have regarding the management of your agroforestry
Farmer does not have specific questions. If he encounters problems can ask his research contact to tell what he has learned abroad...
- What are the key specific economic questions that you have regarding your agroforestry
How to sell the fruit? Where to sell the fruit? How to store the fruit? Who will pick the sea-buckthorn?

6.3 Financial analysis of the orchard system

6.3.1 Description of the modelled agroforestry system

Although the apple trees in the orchard were planted in 2013, it took a long time before the orchard system started was productive. In 2024, the productive apple trees produced about 10-100 kg of apples per tree and the total production was only 1000 kg. Apparently, there were many apple trees which did not produce for reasons such as damage by voles.

Although the orchard was originally proposed as an agroforestry system, during the site visit it was clear that the farmer was not growing a crop between the trees. Hence, because the focus of this study is on agroforestry systems, an alternative scenario was developed. We assumed a wide alley cropping system of apple trees (30 m between tree rows and 3 m between individual trees in the same row) intercropped with a 4 year rotation of winter rye – green manure ley – spring oats – winter rye. This agroforestry system would have a tree density of 88 trees per ha (Figure 40). In real case, this layout would be discussed with the farmer, to double check it is manageable for them from an operational point of view and that it is a solution that would maximise positive impacts for the farmer and the environment.

Figure 40. Suggested layout of wide alley cropping apple system for the east field at Kilpiän Tila.

The apple yield curve used to run the simulated scenario at Kilpiän Tila in Farm-SAFE was the same yield curve as used in the British case study (section 8.3.3) but calibrated for a peak

production of 20 kg of apples per tree at full production, corresponding to years 8-9 (Figure 41, Figure 42), as could be expected for southern Finland conditions.

Figure 41. Apple yield curve created for the Finnish case study (kg tree^{-1}).

Figure 42. Apple yield curve created for the Finnish case study (t ha^{-1}).

The costs associated with the establishment of apple in Finland has previously been reported in Deliverable 2.3 (Cumplido-Marin et al., 2023b). The costs are again summarised in Table 31.

Table 31. Summary of costs for the orchard system in Finland.

Cost	Units	Apple	Pear	Buckthorn (a)	Hazel	Walnut ^(b) / blackcurrant
Tree density	(trees ha ⁻¹)	300	200	0.34 ^(c)	30	50
Establishment						
Cost of plant	(€ tree ⁻¹)	10	3	10	15	5
Cost of individual tree protection	(€ tree ⁻¹)	2	2	1	0	0
Labour ground prep and weeding	(h ha ⁻¹)	10	10	2	0	0
Labour for marking out	(h ha ⁻¹)	2	2	2	0	0
Labour for planting trees	(min tree ⁻¹)	5	5	5	5	5
Labour for tree protection	(min tree ⁻¹)	5	5	5	0	0
Labour for localised weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)	1	1	1	1	1
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30	30	30	30
Weeding						
Year of first weeding	(year)	2014	2020	2020	2020	2020
Year of last weeding	(year)	2023	2023	2023	2023	2023
Annual labour for weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8
Annual cost of weeding	(€ tree ⁻¹)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30	30	30	30
Sward costs						
Establishment of grass sward	(year)	2013	2019	2019	2019	Na
Labour for sward establishment ^(d)	(h ha ⁻¹ grass)	0.5 ^(e)	0.2 ^(f)	0.09 ^(g)	0.08 ^(h)	0
Materials for sward establishment	(€ ha ⁻¹ grass)	30	30	20	0	0
Final year of sward	(year)					
Labour for sward maintenance	(h ha ⁻¹ grass)	3	3	-	3	3
Materials for sward maintenance	(€ ha ⁻¹ grass)	30	30	-	30	30
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30	30	30	30
Epicormic removal						
Year of first removal	(year)	-				
Year of last removal	(year)	-				
Labour for removal	(min tree ⁻¹)	-				
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	-				
Pruning costs						
Height at first prune	(m)	1,5	1			
Minutes per tree at first prune	(min tree ⁻¹)	2	1			
Height at last prune	(m)	2	1.5			
Minutes per tree at last prune	(min tree ⁻¹)	5.5	1			
Removal of prunings	(min tree ⁻¹)	0-1	0			
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30			
Stump removal						
Labour	(min tree ⁻¹)	-				
Removal of tree stumps	(min tree ⁻¹)	-				
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	50 ⁽ⁱ⁾	50	50	50	50
Management						
Labour	(h ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-

na: not applicable

(a) Part of windbreak 2; (b) Part of windbreak 1 (purple line in farm map, Figure 39); (c) 200 trees in 238 m plus 348 m, 3 m wide; (d) 30 min ha; (e) spread by tractor mounted machine; (f) 0.4 ha, spread using hand equipment

(g) 0.18 ha; (h) 5 min; (i) done by contractor

The value of the main revenue sources of the orchard system in Finland are shown in Table 32. Due to the recent establishment of the system, no fruit has been sold as of yet; indicated fruit prices have been estimated based on half the retail price. No grant was available for this particular system at the time of establishment.

Table 32. Initial summary of the anticipated revenue from the orchard system in Finland.

	Unit	Apple ^(a)	Pear ^(a)	Sea buckthorn ^(b)	Hazel	Walnut
Fruit yield ^(c)	(kg ha ⁻¹)	4,122 ^(d)		4,750 ^(e)		
	(kg tree ⁻¹)		67.5 ^(f)		4 ^(g)	6 ^(h)
Fruit value ⁽ⁱ⁾	(€ t ⁻¹)	1,590	1,250	9,000	7,000	8,000
Fruit value	(€ kg ⁻¹)	Pick yourself	Pick yourself	Pick yourself	Pick yourself	Pick yourself
Planting year	(year)	2013	2019	2019	2020-23	2020-23
Value of grant	(€ ha ⁻³)	0	0	0	0	0

* Orchard distributed in an area of 1 ha

^(a) Farmer planning to sell scion wood in the future

^(b) Farmer planning to sell tea and jam in the future

^(c) Estimates

^(d) Source: Omenan viljelyn kannattavuus, presentation ProAgria. Yield is from Uusimaa region

^(e) Yield is from Tyrni viljely, 2015 available online at:

https://jukuri.luke.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/518880/luke-luobio_45_2015.pdf?sequence=4&isAllowed=y ^(h)

^(f) From: <https://wikifarmer.com/pear-tree-harvest-and-yield/> however, this is highly variable

^(g) In Serbia, 3-5 kg per tree from year 7-15, and 5-10 kg/tree from year 15-25. For Finland no data available but probably lower yield: <https://www.hazelnut.co.rs/en/production>

^(h) 7-10 kg/tree in year 5-7. 30-160 kg during the peak production around year 30. In Finland no data on yield available. However, probably much lower yields can be expected (<https://wikifarmer.com/walnut-treearvest-yields/>)

⁽ⁱ⁾ Current fruit production is for self-consumption, price indicated is half of retail price; selling next year onwards; planning direct sell to consumer once it is in production, both fruit and jam

6.4 Results

6.4.1 Rotation and yield of arable and silvoarable systems

Although the arable system and the silvoarable systems have the same crop rotation (winter rye - green manure ley – spring oats – winter rye), we can observe slightly lower yields in the silvoarable system (

Figure 43), due to the competition for water and nutrients consequence of the addition of the apple trees into the system. The mean reduction was about 20%.

Figure 43. Yield of arable crops (left) and simulated yield of silvoarable crops (right).

The simulated yield of apples (t ha⁻¹) obtained after the modelling exercise is shown in Figure 44. The results indicate that the yield of apples will increase from a yield of 0.1 t ha⁻¹ in year 2 to a maximum yield of 1.9 t ha⁻¹ in year 8 and year 9, decreasing afterwards to a yield of 1.3 t ha⁻¹ in year 25.

Figure 44. Silvoarable by-product production from apple trees for the simulated scenario at Kilpiän Tila.

6.4.2 Arable and silvoarable undiscounted costs and benefits

When we analyse the results of the arable and silvoarable undiscounted costs and benefits, we can observe that in the arable system, the undiscounted grant revenue component is a major contributor to the revenue, due to the high grants (749 € ha⁻¹) considered in the exercise (Figure 45). In addition to basic payments, there are grants for organic farming and for measures conserving carbon in agricultural soils. Slightly lower than that, the non-grant revenue is very similar for all harvested crops 500 € ha⁻¹ for winter rye and 539 € ha⁻¹ for spring oats. Arable costs also vary only slightly with the cultivated crop, being cyclic and higher for spring oats (571 € ha⁻¹) and lower for winter rye (471 € ha⁻¹). The green manure ley costs only (56 € ha⁻¹).

Figure 45. Pattern of arable revenue and costs (left) and pattern of silvoarable revenue and costs (right).

Looking in turn at the silvoarable revenue and costs, the undiscounted non-grant revenue makes up the bulk of the revenue. This non-grant revenue is less than 1000 € ha⁻¹ for the first three years and increases steadily over the next few years as the apple yields increase, until it reaches a maximum of 3,356 € ha⁻¹ in year 9. From then onwards, we can observe the silvoarable revenues decreasing again according to the apple yields harvested but still observing the influence of the crop component on those revenues, ending with values of 2525 € ha⁻¹ and 2069 € ha⁻¹ in years 24 and 25 respectively. Silvoarable costs are highest in the first year 2290 € ha⁻¹ and remain relatively steady for the duration of the cultivation period, varying between 280 € ha⁻¹ and 720 € ha⁻¹. In the years when the green manure ley is cultivated, overall revenues and costs decrease accordingly due to the nature of the crop where no yield is harvested.

6.4.3 Arable and silvoarable discounted and undiscounted net margins

We can also observe patterns in the undiscounted and discounted cumulative net margins of the arable and the silvoarable systems (Figure 46). The undiscounted cumulative net margins of the arable system follows a straight line trajectory, from initial values of 778 € ha⁻¹ in year 1 to final values of 18,489 € ha⁻¹ in year 25. The trend in the undiscounted cumulative net margins of the silvoarable system is relatively steep, swiftly increasing from an initial negative value of -1,198 € ha⁻¹ in year 1 to a value of 58,311 € ha⁻¹ in year 25. The discounted cumulative margins of both systems follow similar trends to the undiscounted cumulative net margins but with a reduced incline due to the effect of discounting on the future cost and benefit streams. The initial values in year 1 are identical to the undiscounted values at 778 € ha⁻¹ for the arable system and -1,198 € ha⁻¹ for the silvoarable system, but the final values in year 25 of the rotation are reduced to 12,027 € ha⁻¹ for the arable system and value of 37,968 € ha⁻¹.

Figure 46. Undiscounted cumulative net margins (left) and discounted cumulative net margins (right).

Due to the uncertain nature of the future apple yields a series of apple yields scenarios were modelled to determine their effect on the future silvoarable profitability. These assumed peak yields, of 5, 10, 20, 30, and 40 kg tree⁻¹. The discounted net present values suggested that the profitability of the silvoarable system at 5 kg tree⁻¹ would be marginally lower than the profitability of the arable system by the end of the rotation, but more profitable at a yield of 10 kg tree⁻¹. The yield at which the silvoarable profitability matched the arable profitability as approximately 6.5 kg tree⁻¹, suggesting that any apple yield greater than this would make the silvoarable system more profitable than the arable system.

Figure 30. Discounted cumulative net revenue for different apple yield scenarios relative to the arable system.

6.5 Summary

The financial analysis indicated that the financial return from a system integrating apple trees with an arable crop (assuming a time horizon of 25 years and a discount rate of 4%) were greater than for a sole arable crop (Table 33). This is despite the overall reduction in grant revenue associated with the silvoarable system.

Table 33. Predicted undiscounted, discounted and equivalent annual values (EAVs) (discount rate = 4%) for an apple silvoarable system at Kilpiän Tila.

		Arable	Silvoarable system		
		system	Crop	Tree	Combined
Undiscounted net margin	€ ha ⁻¹	18,489	14,791	43,520	58,311
Undisc. product revenue	€ ha ⁻¹	9,234	7,387	54,725	62,113
Undiscounted grant revenue	€ ha ⁻¹	18,725	14,980	0	14,980
Undiscounted costs	€ ha ⁻¹	9,470	7,576	11,205	18,781
Discounted net margin	€ ha ⁻¹	12,027	9,621	26,346	35,968
Disc. revenue (excl. grants)	€ ha ⁻¹	6,060	4,848	33,556	38,404
Discounted grant revenue	€ ha ⁻¹	12,169	9,735	0	9,735
Discounted costs	€ ha ⁻¹	6,203	4,962	7,209	12,171
EAV of net margin	€ ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	770	616	1,686	2,302
EAV of revenue (excl. grants)	€ ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	388	310	2,148	2,458
EAV of grant revenue	€ ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	779	623	0	623
EAV of costs	€ ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹	397	318	461	779

A key feature of this benefit is associated with eliminating the need for harvesting, boxing, and storage costs for the apples, since it is assumed that the apples will be harvested by pick-your-own visitors to the farm. However in practice, a pick-your-own system will require

management in terms of ensuring that there is someone available to help visitors park and transact the pick-your-own purchases. Such costs were not assumed in the current analysis.

The assumed undiscounted grant revenue for the arable system (18,725 € ha⁻¹) was greater than for the silvoarable system (14,980 € ha⁻¹). This is due to the reduction in crop area in the silvoarable system (80% of the total system area). In addition, there was no grant income associated with the tree component of the silvoarable system to compensate for the loss of grants payable on the crop component.

Despite the lower grant, the net margin of the silvoarable system exceeded the net margin of the arable system. The undiscounted net margin for the silvoarable system (58,311 € ha⁻¹) was 3.2 times that of the arable system (18,489 € ha⁻¹). The discounted net margin for the silvoarable system (38,695 € ha⁻¹) was 3.0 times that of the arable system (12,027 € ha⁻¹). This was essentially because the product revenue from apples in the silvoarable system was so much greater than that from the arable systems. The undiscounted product revenue for the silvoarable system (62,112 € ha⁻¹) was 6.7 times that of the arable system (9,234 € ha⁻¹). Discounting reduced this, but the discounted product revenue for the silvoarable system (38,404 € ha⁻¹) was still 6.3 times that of the arable system (6,060 € ha⁻¹). On the other hand, both undiscounted costs for the silvoarable system 18,781 € ha⁻¹ was approximately double that for the arable system (9,470 € ha⁻¹).

7 Czech case study

7.1 Background to case study and assumptions

For the Czech case study farm, we chose the organic farm Rosičky of Mr. Čeludová and Ms. Ježek in Výstrčenovice near the town of Jihlava in South East Bohemia (Figure 47), with a total size of around 50 ha (6.4 ha of arable land, 43.7 ha of permanent grassland – pastures and meadows). Their farm is located in the hilly landscape of Vysočina at 500 to 600 m asl with average annual precipitation of 650 mm. The farmer breeds a main herd of beef cattle (20 head) and the main product is the selling of beef when animals reach a live weight of 250 kg.

Figure 47. Location of the Czech study case farm, Rosičky, in south-central Czechia.

In autumn 2023, the farmer established a new agroforestry system with the help of new incentives for the establishment and management of agroforestry on three meadow parcels, 9,6 ha in total, 100 trees per ha planted in 10 rows. They used a mix of forest trees, Table 34, with species mixed in each line (two forest trees and one fruit tree). In 2024, they established more agroforestry on 8 plots in a total area of 11.2 ha.

Many farms in the Bohemian-Moravian Highlands (Vysočina) have large fields (up to 50 ha) and intensive agriculture is practiced by agro-business companies. By establishing an agroforestry system on permanent grassland, the farmer wanted to diversify the source of farm products by producing wood and timber in the long term, quality fruit production in the short term alongside quality hay and haylage on the allocated fields. Thanks to the implementation of a diverse agroforestry system, they expect an increase in biodiversity on the planted plots. They are expecting increased numbers of insects, birds and mammals, but also hoping to improve the aesthetic character of the landscape with the planting of agroforestry. Additionally, the farmers have a vision, that the adoption of agroforestry can help to adapt to and mitigate against the ongoing effects of climate change (i.e. increased water retention, increased soil health, habitat and shelter creation, cooling effect).

The trees were planted in lines on three fields (see Figure 48) with a distance between lines on all three plots of 18-20 m. The lines are also 18 to 20 m away from the edge in all the plots. The distance between trees in the lines is 3 to 6 m apart. The grass will be cut around the planted trees. The plots have an approximate north-south orientation.

Agroforestry plot 1. (LPIS/DPB 6603/8)

– Area 4.15 ha.

Tree lines from the left) 415 pcs. woody plants:

- 1 Oak, maple, sour cherry, apple,
- 2 Oak, maple, pear, apple,
- 3 Oak, maple, apple,
- 4 Oak, maple, apple,
- 5 Oak, maple, alder, apple, plum,
- 6 - Oak, maple, alder, apple, plum

b) Agroforestry plot 2. (LPIS/DPB 6603/18)

–area 2.31 ha

(Line from the left) 231 pcs. woody plants,

- 1 - Oak, maple, alder, sour cherry, apple,
- 2 - Oak, maple, alder, pear, apple,
- Oak, maple, alder, apple, plum

Agroforestry Plot 3. (LPIS/DPB no, 6603/2)

–area 3.19 ha

Line from left) 319 pcs. woody plants:

- 1. Oak, maple, alder, Sour cherry, apple, pear,
- 2. Oak, maple, alder, apple and plum

Figure 48. Fields where agroforestry was implemented at Rosičky, and design of the agroforestry system within a) Agroforestry Plot 1; b) Agroforestry plot 2; and c) Agroforestry plot 3.

The planted trees was at least 120 cm tall comprising a range of tree species (Table 34).

Table 34. List and number of trees planted.

Name	Latin name	N. plants
Forest trees		650
Maple	<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	300
Alder	<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	50
Oak	<i>Quercus robur</i>	300
Fruit trees		315
Apple	<i>Malus domestica</i>	80
Plum	<i>Prunus domestica</i>	185
Pear	<i>Pyrus communis</i>	30
Sour cherry	<i>Prunus cerasus</i>	20
Total number		965

7.2 Qualitative evaluation

7.2.1 Background to case study and assumptions

Prior to completing a financial analysis, the farmer was asked to describe the main characteristics of the system.

- How much land have you used for the agroforestry system?
Total 20.5 ha: 2023 – 9.5 ha, 2024 – 11.2 ha, permanent grassland (8 plots; 40% of the farm).
- Which tree species did you choose? Have they grown well?
75% Forest trees (small-leaved linden, pedunculate oak, milk maple, sticky alder where it is humid), 25% fruit trees (plums, apple, pear and sour cherries). Destruction by animals, especially in forest trees. There must be better protection of trees, welded mesh. I do not use watering, in dry places (on the hill) some seedlings have dried up. The seedlings and species are suitable for our cold region.
- What density did you plant them at? Do you think you will thin them during the rotation? If so, in which year?
100 trees per ha, rapid rotation for maple on wood chips after 10 years. Rotation for other forest trees 40-50 years.
- How did you manage the tree strip area? Do you still have to manage it in any particular way?
Used as a meadow, mowed twice a year, 20 m distance between tree lines, 3-4 m row spacing. Small garden tractor mulching under trees.
- What crops/livestock are you using in the rows between the trees? Do you think this will evolve over time as the trees grow bigger?

At this moment only use for cutting and haymaking, flowery meadow. After trees grow back, more moisture, better grass growth, reduced wind erosion.

- Do you plan to plant more plots of agroforestry in the future? If so why/why not?
Yes, expand to pastures and try rotational grazing of cattle. Improve animal welfare and pasture quality.
- Would you do your agroforestry in the same way again if you knew what you know now?
Probably the same way. I would like to try planting trees on the edge of the plot.

In terms of identifying the benefits and disadvantages of the agroforestry system, the first observation was that the farmer wanted to cultivate fruit trees (Table 35). The farmer reported “I wanted to have an orchard”. The second reason was to improve the aesthetic appearance of the farm, as well as the support of biodiversity and improvement of the environment. The existing subsidy is a significant economic motive. Tree lines can also act as a windbreak. The farmer reported that the financial support for agroforestry was “very good”, and that “agroforestry looks good and other people like it too”.

Table 35. Example perceived benefits and disadvantages of the silvopastoral agroforestry systems in Czechia.

Benefits of system	Disadvantages of system
<i>Production of fruits, woodchips and timber and potential revenue</i>	<i>Costs of establishment and management (but it can be well covered by investment subsidy)</i>
<i>Continued grass production for hay and haylage</i>	<i>Costs of tree management (it can be covered by the subsidy for agroforestry management)</i>
<i>Reduction of wind erosion and microclimate change</i>	<i>Potential loss in grass yield in later years</i>
<i>Attracting more biodiversity</i>	<i>Damage of the trees by wildlife – need for intensive tree protection</i>
<i>Aesthetic appearance of the farm</i>	<i>Climate change - death of the trees caused by summer draught, damage of the blooms by late frost, attack of pest and diseases</i>
<i>Subsidy programme</i>	

The next set of questions related to the opportunities and barriers to implementing the agroforestry system.

- What have been the key challenges/barriers to establishing and managing your system? Were there any challenges associated with finding the trees, learning how to look after trees, managing the crops or animals between the trees, using machinery?
The subsidy program was launched late and in the first year (2023) there was a problem with the purchase of seedlings. The following year everything was fine. Some basic knowledge, such as design is easy to do on a computer, but what is proposed is more difficult to implement in the field. Planting and maintaining trees is not a problem. A lot of information can now be found.

- What particular opportunities and benefits do you think the outputs of your agroforestry system provide? Are you using the outputs to satisfy a need on the farm? Do you have a sales outlet for your tree products? Do you process and sell the products yourself? Do you have a restaurant, holiday let, or farm shop where you sell the products?

So far, we only have hay from meadows, but in the future, we want to produce woodchips from maples and in the long term wood from forest trees. In the medium term, fruit (plums, apples, pears). We want to try selling fruit by self-harvesting.

The final set of questions related to the farmer's main technical, economic, or management questions.

- What are the technical/economic/management questions that keep you awake at night!
Climate change causes attacks by diseases and pests, damage to blooms by late frost, but also summer droughts cause the death of trees. Protection against animals - biting and knocking out.
- How can our team help answer specific questions that you have regarding the management of your agroforestry?
Suitability of the tree species composition for my conditions. Find more resistant tree species against late frosts.
- What are the key specific economic questions that you have regarding your agroforestry?
State support is sufficient for the establishment and management of agroforestry.

7.3 Availability of agroforestry support in Czechia

Agroforestry has gained quite a lot of interest the Czechia in last decade as a promising measure to maintain food production whilst improving biodiversity, soil erosion control, and moderating weather extremes (Quinkenstein et al., 2018).

The Ministry of Agriculture in cooperation with the Ministry of the Environment and experts endorsed a special subsidy (investment intervention) as part of the Czech strategic plan of the CAP (2023-2027) for the establishment of agroforestry systems in 2023. This incentive covers the establishment of agroforestry in first year (4 353 € ha⁻¹) and also 5 years of support for the maintenance of the system (754 € ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) which can be extended for another 5 years. The subsidy measure contributes to three CAP specific objectives:

- (i) to contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation, including reducing greenhouse gas emissions and enhancing carbon sequestration, as well as to promote sustainable energy;
- (ii) to foster sustainable development and the efficient management of natural resources such as water, soil and air, including reducing chemical dependency;
- (iii) to contribute to halting and reversing biodiversity loss, enhance ecosystem services and preserve habitats and landscapes.

The main conditions and requirements of the subsidy include: planting of 100 trees ha⁻¹; a minimum of three tree species in agroforestry (none over 40%); one of the tree species must be a forest species and there must be a minimum of one fruit tree species; maintenance for 5 years with survival of 75% trees, tree strips can be 2-10 wide and must be inside the plot (not around e.g. no hedges). A list of permitted and subsidized tree species has been published, containing 46 forest and 13 fruit species, which may be modified in the future. The soil under the trees remains standard arable land, grassland, or permanent grassland.

The subsidy is considered to be quite successful as more than 61000 trees (610 ha) were planted in 1 year and 2/3 of the allocated money has already been used after the first year and supplemental financial resources will be allocated for the remaining years of the current CAP (2023-2027). The subsidy is also important part of the motivation for farmers as it is very positively influencing economic efficiency of established agroforestry.

7.3.1 Modelling agroforestry with Final ALS

The Final ALS model was developed in Czechia to examine the financial viability of silvoarable agroforestry systems (AFS). It does this in two ways:

- Analysis of the economic efficiency of tree component of AFS to find the minimum price of produced wood and/or fruits that would ensure the farmer reaches the desired economic effect. This analysis evaluates the given inputs valued at market prices and the amount of biomass produced, including distribution over time (Králík et al., 2022).
- Analysis of the economic efficiency of wood biomass (woodchips) from AFS considering possible opportunities for land use — typical for conventional agricultural production (Knápek et al., 2017).

Final ALS was developed using previous model Final3 E, which was used for plantations of short rotation coppice (SRC)(Havlíčková et al, 2011) and recently adapted for silvopastoral AFS with narrow strips of SRC called Coppice Tree Belts (CTB) (Králík et al., 2022). It was used for calculation of woodchip production from willow hedges at Dutch case study farm (see chapter 5.5).

The silvopastoral system in the Czech case study farm was established with 10 tree lines and 965 trees on three pasture plots, covering a total area of 9.6 ha. The assortment of planted trees includes three forest species and four fruit tree species, e.g. namely, oak, maple, alder, apple, plum, sour cherry, and pear.

The following assumptions were made using the Final ALS tool.

- 2024 prices were used.
- The lifetime of the agroforestry system is 40 years.
- Income tax is 21 %.
- Nominal discount is 7,1 %.
- Escalation of prices is 2 % per year.
- Investment subsidy is 4 353 € ha⁻¹ for planting (the second year).

- Maintenance subsidy 754 € ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ for established systems (5 + 5 years from 2nd year).
- The principal production period of fruit trees (apple and plum) is 5 to 15 years; then yields decrease gradually by 20 % per year (self-picking harvest is expected for low prices).
- The production period of forest trees (longer than the chosen modeling period; oak = 80 years, maple = 60 years) was terminated at 40 years with proportionally lower wood production.

Final ALS, which is being developed within the DigitAF project, can be used to determine the economic efficiency of silvoarable agroforestry systems. As the Czech case study farm is primarily a cattle farm, we have **modelled only the tree component** of their agroforestry system. We simulated cash flows of the agroforestry and calculated NPV. The minimum price of production, (based on the net present value criterion), was performed to enable the assessment of tree production.

The main costs associated with the establishment of the agroforestry system in the Czech case study farm are presented in Table 36. All input data were verified and upgraded with the farmer before modelling, including harvest cost of fruits, cost of water, etc. The costs of trees varied between €3.9 and €6.4 per tree.

Table 36. Input table of costs for tree component of agroforestry system (The values have been converted from the Czech Krona to €).

	Cost	Units	Value
Establishment	Oak plant	€ tree ⁻¹	4.84
	Maple plant	€ tree ⁻¹	4.62
	Alder plant	€ tree ⁻¹	3.85
	Plum, apple, or pear plant	€ tree ⁻¹	6.38
	Sour cherry plant	€ tree ⁻¹	6.38
	Marking out	h ha ⁻¹	3
	Planting	h tree ⁻¹	0.367
	Tree protection	€ tree ⁻¹	2.5
	Protection	h tree ⁻¹	0.183
	Cost of labour	€ h ⁻¹	13
Weeding		h tree ⁻¹	0.333
		€ h ⁻¹	13
Epicormic removal		h tree ⁻¹	0.083
		€ h ⁻¹	13
Pruning	Non-fruit	h tree ⁻¹	0.250
		€ h ⁻¹	13
	Fruit	h tree ⁻¹	0.333
		€ h ⁻¹	13
Irrigation		h ha ⁻¹	20
		€ h ⁻¹	20
Clear felling		h tree ⁻¹	0.5
		€ h ⁻¹	20

Stump removal	h tree ⁻¹	0.5
	€ h ⁻¹	20

The area, and anticipated production from the trees is provided in Table 35.

Table 37. Area, quantity and revenues of planted trees.

Tree species	Number	Area (ha)	Firewood (m ³ tree ⁻¹)	Firewood value (€ m ⁻³)	Felling size (m ³ tree ⁻¹)	Felling value (€ m ⁻³)
Oak	280	2.8	1.5	120	1	4 000
Maple	280	2.8	1.5	120	1	4 000
Alder	50	0.5	1.5	120	1	2 000
			in year 40	growth 2 %	in year 40	growth 2 %
			Fruit yield (kg tree ⁻¹)	Fruit price (€ kg ⁻¹)		
Plum	185	1.85	60	0.6		
Apple	80	0.8	100	1		
Pear	30	0.3	100	1		
Sour cherry	20	0.2	35	0.6		
				growth 2 %		
Aggregate	925	9.25				

7.4 Results

The Final-ALS model predicted that the net present value of the agroforestry (over 40 years) would be 191,000 € (Table 38, Figure 49). Because of the tree planting subsidy in the second year, the agroforestry system was able to show a positive return by the second year, resulting in an internal rate of return of 70% from tree planting. All the data was provided by the farmer, but it is possible that the value of timber may be overestimated, and the cost of expenditure like irrigation may be underestimated. Nevertheless, the presence of the subsidy suggests that planting trees can make financial sense.

Table 38. The financial output from the Final ALS model of the agroforestry system at the Rosička farm including net present value (NPV) and the internal rate of return (IRR) over 40 years from 2025 to 2064, assuming a discount rate of 7.1%.

Financial criteria	Year			
	2025	2026	2027	2028
Annual cash flow (€ yr ⁻¹)	-21,000	34,000	-3,000	-2,000
Cumulative cash flow (€)	-21,000	13,000	10,000	8,000
Cumulative discounted cash flow (€)	-21,000	11,000	8,000	6,000
Net present value (NPV) (€ over 40 years)	191,000			
Internal rate of return (%)	70.4%			
Annual equivalent value of the cash flow (€ yr ⁻¹)	15			
Payback Period Ts (simple) (years)	1			

Figure 49. Predicted a) annual cashflow, b) cumulative cashflow, and c) cumulative discounted cash flow (discount rate = 7.1%) for the tree component of agroforestry at the Czechia case study farm, Rosička farm– fruit and forest trees.

The results of our first modelling of the economic effectiveness of the tree component of agroforestry in the Rosička farm, show that current subsidies are covering all establishment cost and create a positive economic result of this system (See Table 38 and Figure 50). The subsidy thus plays a key role for the introduction of agroforestry systems in Czech agriculture and allows for the collection of first experiences with this innovative system in our conditions. Financial data and also practical knowledge collected from farmers will allow for future selection of best practices and tree combinations for future improvement without such good subsidy or even without it.

8 British case study

8.1 Background to case study and assumptions

For the UK case study farm is Hope Farm located in Knapwell, Cambridgeshire in Eastern England. It is a 181 ha commercially managed arable farm owned by the Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (RSPB).

Within the 181 ha of the farm, one 11 ha field was allocated to silvoarable agroforestry with the objective of increasing farm biodiversity and diversifying farm outputs (Figure 50). The silvoarable system, established by staff and volunteers, is an alley-cropping system using three types of trees (Figure 51), in total 1,000 trees:

- Apple trees of 13 varieties
- Cobnut trees of 3 varieties
- Broadleaf shelter belt trees of six species to provide a wind break, consisting of field maple, small leaved lime, hornbeam, wild cherry, hawthorn, and common alder

Figure 50. Aerial view of farm boundary (red) and agroforestry field (yellow) at Hope Farm, Cambridgeshire, UK.

Figure 51. Diagram of agroforestry design in the British case study.

8.2 Qualitative evaluation

Prior to completing a financial analysis, the farmer was asked to describe the main characteristics of the system.

- How much land have you used for the agroforestry system?
11 ha.
- Which tree species did you choose?
Cobnuts, apples, hawthorn, small leaved lime, field maple, common alder, hornbeam, rowan, wild service tree, wild cherry.
- Have they all grown well?
Good: cobnuts, apples, hawthorn, wild cherry.*
OK: small leaved lime, field maple, hornbeam, rowan, wild service tree.
Bad: common alder.
**cobnuts only lost in first year due to supplier issue, but second year have grown well.*
- Would you use the same tree species again?
Yes to all the above other than common alder as is better suited to a wetter climate – only put in as a native alternative to the popular Italian alder.
- What density did you plant them at? Do you think you will thin them during the rotation? If so, in which year?
Apples every 5 m, single line, 30 m apart. The rest are 2 lines in 2 m x 2 m spacing, 30 m apart from each other. All rows separated by a strip of arable.
- How did you manage the tree strip area? Do you still have to manage it in any particular way?

Rotationally cut understory in the autumn of wildflowers and grasses (planted in 2021). Thistles also cut throughout the growing season.

- What crops/livestock are you using in the rows between the trees? Do you think this will evolve over time as the trees grow bigger?
No livestock. Arable rotation system with combinable crops such as wheat, barley, oats, oilseed rape, beans, with some cover crops.
- Do you plan to plant more plots of agroforestry in the future? If so why/why not?
Not until we have full evidence of this agroforestry impact including a financial return.
- Would you do your agroforestry in the same way again if you knew what you know now?
Same layout, plant sequentially and consider water availability. Have adapted guarding for durability and better protection, so would do this from the start (e.g. vole guards, taller plastic guards, stronger stakes). Would mulch all the trees with woodchip.

In terms of identifying the benefits and disadvantages of the agroforestry system, the benefits included a greater number of insects and potential soil and carbon benefits. However, they also noted that the system was really expensive in terms of time and financing (Table 39).

Table 39. Table of perceived benefits and challenges/disadvantages of the walnuts in grassland system.

Benefits of system	Challenges/Disadvantages of system
<i>More insects about</i>	<i>Really expensive in time and finances</i>
<i>Community engagement</i>	<i>Complicates your business</i>
<i>Potential soil and carbon benefits</i>	<i>Is a steep learning curve learning how to look after the system even with access to advice.</i>
	<i>There are very few people who are experts in agroforestry i.e. you couldn't easily hire an agroforestry contractor or manager</i>
<i>When up and running, should be more diverse with more income – but we haven't got there yet</i>	<i>Reduced income from field for the first 5 years</i>
<i>Looks nice, but the flowers have a big impact on that</i>	
<i>Full impacts on biodiversity not yet determined for our site</i>	

The next set of questions related to the opportunities and barriers to implementing the agroforestry system.

- What have been the key challenges/barriers to establishing and managing your system? Were there any challenges associated with finding the trees, learning how to look after trees, managing the crops or animals between the trees, using machinery?
Difficult to find UK sourced trees (rootstock) as a lot say UK grown, but rootstock isn't UK grown – that's a requirement as us as an RSPB site

*Lots of issues about learning to look after the trees particularly in this sort of system – pruning, pests, planting techniques, how to stake and guard, watering
Advice is limited and not easy to find what is appropriate for you
Establishing a long term vision that will work for the business and ensure we have a supply chain we're aiming for before planting.*

- What particular opportunities and benefits do you think the outputs of your agroforestry system provide? Are you using the outputs to satisfy a need on the farm? Do you have a sales outlet for your tree products? Do you process and sell the products yourself? Do you have a restaurant, holiday let, or farm shop where you sell the products?

Many benefits not realised as we aren't in the production phase yet.

Outputs will go to be sold in RSPB shops, diversifying outlets and giving us more control of our crop prices / income (hopefully).

Products should be processed locally.

The final set of questions related to the farmer's main technical, economic, or management questions.

- What are the technical/economic/management questions that keep you awake at night?
Are they being eaten? Pests which are out of our control and which we have no experience in dealing with yet. Economically when will it start returning, and will it get to the financial potential projected initially.

- How can our team help answer specific questions that you have regarding the management of your agroforestry ?

Happy to share all the pitfalls of establishment, and contribute to an advice hub that gathers advice from different places.

Results from our monitoring on the impact on biodiversity, finances and carbon.

Is there a supply chain other than our own shops that we can go into, that will deliver enough income?

- What are the specific economic questions that you have regarding your agroforestry ?
Want to know now they're in, when they will be profitable. When we were planning it, we wanted to know what species are going to be the most likely to deliver an economic return, but able to be processed at a cost-effective price for sale, and yield well enough to return a good income.

Scale of agroforestry plantation for it to be manageable and profitable.

8.3 Financial analysis using Farm-SAFE

8.3.1 Principles of financial analysis in Farm-SAFE

Because agroforestry systems exist over multiple years, a common feature of the financial modelling of tree-based systems is the need to account for preference for money in the present. Hence future benefits and costs can be given “present values” using a “discount factor” to systematically reduce their current importance as the time that has elapsed since the start of the project increases. The present value of the costs and benefits over the defined time horizon are then aggregated into a single value known as the net present value (*NPV*; units: € ha⁻¹) where the revenue (R_t), variable costs (V_t), and assignable fixed costs (A_t) are specified for each year (t) over a time horizon of T (years) with i as the discount rate (Equation 5).

$$NPV = \sum_{t=0}^{t=T} \frac{(R_t - V_t - A_t)}{(1 + i)^t} \quad \text{Equation 5.}$$

The Farm-SAFE model (Graves et al., 2011) was applied to obtain the financial benefits and costs of the agroforestry system at Hope Farm. The original Farm-SAFE model was developed by Cranfield (UK) in 2006 as part of the European Union sponsored SAFE project (2001-2005) (Graves et al., 2011). The Microsoft Excel model was developed to compare the financial aspects of arable, forestry and agroforestry systems using discounted cash flow analysis for up to 60 years. The model is able to model arable, forestry, and silvoarable systems across four areas of a farm or region to determine the feasibility and implications of introducing agroforestry across four areas of a farm or region to determine the feasibility and implications of agroforestry systems on European farms.

8.3.2 Yield, cost, and price data for arable crops

For the agroforestry system at Hope Farm, the financial modelling used a combination of data from the literature and from conversations with the farm managers to identify the costs and benefits of production. The predictions from this modelling were then compared to the costs and benefits associated with a standard arable system which acted as a counterfactual. The crop yield data is shown in

Table 40. The rotation and yields of grain for five arable crops (

Table 40). were provided by the farm manager during the data gathering process via interview with the researchers.

The by-product (straw) yield (y_{bp}) was calculated as a percentage (%) of the total biomass yield (y_{mc}) using Equation 6. For the above crops, the percentages applied were 50% for winter wheat, winter barley, and spring barley; 55% for winter oil seed rape; 65% for winter beans.

$$y_{bp} = \frac{1}{1/2} * y_{mc} * (1 - \%) \quad \text{Equation 6.}$$

Table 40. Crop yield data and by-product yield data for the arable rotation at Hope Farm.

Crop	Crop yield (t ha ⁻¹)	By-product yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Winter wheat (<i>Triticum aestivum</i>)	7.70	7.70
Winter barley (<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>)	6.25	6.25
Winter oilseed rape (<i>Brassica napus</i> L. var. <i>napus</i>)	3.20	3.91
Winter beans (<i>Vicia faba</i>)	4.00	7.43
Spring barley (<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>)	3.50	3.50

The prices and costs associated with the crop rotation at Hope Farm are shown in Table 41.

Table 41. Prices and costs for arable system at Hope Farm.

Costs	Units	Winter wheat	Winter barley	Winter oilseed rape	Winter beans	Spring barley
Grain price	£ t ⁻¹	264.00	258.00	515.00	300.00	258.00
By-product* price (e.g. straw)	£ t ⁻¹	76.00	70.00	0.00	0.00	70.00
Area payment	£ ha ⁻¹	180.00	180.00	180.00	180.00	180.00
Seed price	£ kg ⁻¹	0.60	0.62	0.52	0.30	0.62
Seed rate	kg ha ⁻¹	200.00	191.00	19.00	250.00	191.00
Fertiliser price	£ (kg N) ⁻¹	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.32
Fertiliser rate	l ha ⁻¹	690.00	400.00	515.13	90.14	400.00
Spray price	£ application ⁻¹	52.49	40.65	40.65	40.77	40.65
Spray rate	app ha ⁻¹	6	3	5	4	3
Other price	£ unit ⁻¹	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00
Other rate	units ha ⁻¹	4.00	4.50	6.00	3.75	4.50
Total variable costs	£ ha ⁻¹	715.34	435.87	467.88	323.17	435.87
Assignable fixed costs (excluding labour)	£ ha ⁻¹	305.00	263.00	242.00	222.00	263.00

8.3.3 Agroforestry system yields, prices, and costs

Arable component: the arable intercrop area of the silvoarable system was calculated to occupy 80% of the total area, whilst the tree strips, being spaced at 30 m row intervals, and being 6m wide, occupied 20% of the total area. Given that the tree strips were 6m wide, and that the dwarf apple trees, which would be pruned to be no higher than about 2.5 m so that they could be harvested whilst standing on the ground, would divert little light or water from the crop, it was assumed that the crop yield in the intercrop area, would also be maintained at 80% of the crop yield in the arable system throughout the rotation.

Tree component: since no model for dwarf apple trees exists within Yield-SAFE, a simple expert-based model was developed to predict future apple yields for Hope Farm. A typical apple yield profile for dwarf apple trees was obtained from Lampkin et al. (2023) (Figure 52a). This showed that yields although low in the initial five years, increase rapidly to provide maximum yields between years 5 – 11, after which yields decline to a steady state. Typically, a rotation may last 20 years. However, here a slightly longer rotation was anticipated by Hope

Farm managers, and the yields were therefore extrapolated to year 25. Since the yield data here were given on a per hectare basis, but are required for the financial modelling to be on a per tree basis, the per hectare data were adjusted to a per tree basis using the planting density of the orchard, 3.5 m x 2 m (Figure 52b).

Figure 52. Yield profile a) per hectare and b) per trees for dwarf apple trees for a planting density of 3.5 m x 2 m (black dash line) and fitted interpolation for yield profile (blue continuous line).

Given that trees in orchards are planted at a much higher density than trees in silvoarable systems, a multiplier was added to the apple yield model to allow calibration adjustments to be made for dwarf apple trees in silvoarable systems. However, relatively few data could be found for real tree systems located nearby with similar environmental conditions. Those available from the literature and reports from farm visits are summarised in Table 42 and plotted in Figure 53.

Table 42. Apple yield data found in the literature.

Source	Harvest year	Tree density (trees/ha)	Harvest amount (t/ha)	Harvest amount (kg/tree)
Agroforestry Handbook	3	90	1.1	12
Agroforestry Handbook (Briggs and Knight, 2019)	8	90	6.0	67
Friends of the Earth article (Friends of The Earth, 2020)	5	85	0.5	5.7
FWF field visit report (Pilbeam, 2017)	8	85	6.5	76.5
Friends of the Earth article (Friends of The Earth, 2020)	5	123*	0.5	3.9
FWF field visit report (Pilbeam, 2017)	8	123	6.5	52.8

* tree density excluding ditch margin area.

Given that some of these data are themselves also estimates, rather than measured data, it was assumed that apple yields in the Hope Farm silvoarable system on a per tree basis at 83 trees ha⁻¹ should be the greater than those for an orchard system at 1429 trees ha⁻¹. In discussion with the farm managers at Hope Farm, a yield of around 45 kg tree⁻¹ appeared to be consistent with their expectations for a peak yield (Figure 53), equivalent to 3.7 t ha⁻¹ during the peak yield phase (see Figure 55). This would appear to be a somewhat conservative yield profile, if the yield estimates in

Table 42 are correct, but is greater than the per tree apple yields in the densely planted orchard reported in Lampkin et al., (2023).

Figure 53. Real yield data collected from farms in the same region of the UK and yield simulation for Hope Farm.

The value of the main revenue sources of the alley cropping system are shown in the brief summary table for the British case study (Table 43). Due to the recent establishment of the system (2021), the apple yield indicated is an estimation based on a nearby farm in the same region of England and the apple price has been obtained from a British database (2023 prices). No reliable source of data for hazelnuts was found at the time of data gathering.

Table 43. Assumptions regarding sources of revenue for the silvoarable system in the UK.

Item	Units	Value	Units	Value
Subsidies	£ ha ⁻¹	57.00	€ ha ⁻¹	65.66
Apple price	£ kg ⁻¹	1.10 ^(a)	€ kg ⁻¹	1.28 (a)

^(a) Price extracted from <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistical-data-sets/wholesale-fruit-and-vegetable-prices-weekly-average> for gala apples (lowest price).

The main costs associated with the establishment of the silvoarable system (tree component) in the UK are presented in Table 44.

Table 44. Input table of costs for tree component of the Hope Farm silvoarable system.

Inputs	Units	Costs of apple tree component (£)	Units	Costs of apple tree component (€*)
Number of trees	(n)	200	(n)	200
Tree density	(n ha ⁻¹)	83	(n ha ⁻¹)	83
Establishment				
Cost of plant (average 1-2 year old)	(£ tree ⁻¹)	23.75	(€ tree ⁻¹)	27.36
Cost of individual tree protection	(£ tree ⁻¹)	6.16	(€ tree ⁻¹)	7.10
Labour for ground prep ^(a)	(hr ha ⁻¹)	1.60	(hr ha ⁻¹)	1.60
Labour for full weeding	(hr ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-
Labour for marking out ^(a)	(hr ha ⁻¹)	11.90	(hr ha ⁻¹)	11.90
Labour for planting trees	(min tree ⁻¹)	5.00	(min tree ⁻¹)	5.00
Labour for tree protection	(min tree ⁻¹)	5.00	(min tree ⁻¹)	5.00
Labour for localised weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)	-	(min tree ⁻¹)	-
Weeding (mowing)				
Year of first weeding	(year)	1	(year)	1
Year of last weeding	(year)	4	(year)	4
Annual labour for weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)	5.00	(min tree ⁻¹)	5.00
Annual cost of weeding ^(b)	(£ tree ⁻¹)	3.66	(€ ha ⁻¹)	4.22
Watering				
Year of first watering	(year)	1	(year)	1
Year of last watering	(year)	2	(year)	2
Annual labour for watering	(min tree ⁻¹)	53.23	(min tree ⁻¹)	53.23
Annual material cost of watering ^(c)	(£ tree ⁻¹)	0.16	(€ tree ⁻¹)	0.18
Wildflower strips				
Establishment of wildflowers strips	(year)	1	(year)	1
Labour for wild flower establishment ^(d)	(hr ha ⁻¹)	8.00	(hr ha ⁻¹)	8.00
Materials for wildflower establishment ^(d)	(£ ha ⁻¹)	1982.50	(€ ha ⁻¹)	2283.64
Final year of wildflower strips	(year)	25	(year)	25

Labour for wildflower maintenance ^(d)	(h ha ⁻¹)	17.50	(h ha ⁻¹)	1.60
Materials for annual wildflower maintenance	(£ ha ⁻¹)	-	(€ ha ⁻¹)	-
Pruning				
Height at first prune ^(f)	(m)	1.20	(m)	1.20
Minutes per tree at first prune	(min tree ⁻¹)	5.00	(min tree ⁻¹)	5.00
Height at last prune ^(g)	(m)	3.00	(m)	3.00
Minutes per tree at last prune	(min tree ⁻¹)	3.00	(min tree ⁻¹)	3.00
Removal of prunings ^(h)	(min tree ⁻¹)	1.00	(min tree ⁻¹)	1.00
Maintenance				
Administrative cost	(£ ha ⁻¹)	80.00	(€ ha ⁻¹)	92.15
Insurance management	(£ ha ⁻¹)	-	(€ ha ⁻¹)	-
Packaging				
Harvesting	(£ ha ⁻¹)	98.30	(€ ha ⁻¹)	113.23
Grading and packing	(£ t ⁻¹)	121.50	(€ t ⁻¹)	139.96
Storage and bin hire	(£ t ⁻¹)	86.80	(€ t ⁻¹)	99.98
Transport	(£ t ⁻¹)	127.30	(€ t ⁻¹)	146.64
Clear felling (contractor)				
Time	(min tree ⁻¹)	5.00	(min tree ⁻¹)	5.00
Cost	(£ h ⁻¹)	80.00	(€ h ⁻¹)	92.15

* exchange rate £/€ = 1.15

^(a) estimated cost per tree = (2 £ m⁻³) * (2 t water day⁻¹) * (3 days week⁻¹) * (12 weeks) / (11 ha) / (83 tree ha⁻¹)

^(b) calculated from contractor cost of £333 ha⁻¹ * (11 ha) / (1000 trees)

^(c) establishment hours are at around 500 for planting, 500 watering first year, including volunteer groups that were used for engagement purposes and were far more than a contractor would have needed to complete the work

^(d) adjusted original data to reflect real area of wildflower strips (*100/20): labour for wildflower strips establishment (1.6 hr); materials for wildflower strip establishment (396.5 hr ha⁻¹); labour for annual wildflower maintenance (3.5 hr ha⁻¹)

^(e) currently do not pay for maintenance machinery as it is done for free by a neighbour

^(f) had first prune in tree nursery; not pruned yet at farm

^(g) Unsure when final year is

^(h) first prune was so small that the prunings were left in wildflower strips

8.3.4 Rotation and yield of arable and silvoarable systems

Although the arable system and the silvoarable systems have the same crop rotation (winter wheat – winter barley – winter oil seed rape – winter wheat – spring barley – winter beans), we can observe slightly lower yields in the silvoarable system (Figure 54), due to the competition for water and nutrients consequence of the addition of the apple trees into the system. Crops yields are reduced by 20% for all arable crops i.e. winter wheat, winter barley, winter oil seed rape, spring barley, and winter beans.

Figure 54. Yield of arable crops (left) and simulated yield of silvoarable crops (right).

The simulated yield of apples (t ha⁻¹) obtained after the modelling exercise is shown in Figure 55. The results indicate that the yield of apples will increase from a yield of 0.12 t ha⁻¹ in year 1 to a maximum yield of 3.72 t ha⁻¹ in year 8 and year 9, decreasing afterwards to a yield of 2.60 t ha⁻¹ in year 25.

Figure 55. Silvoarable by-product production from apple trees.

8.3.5 Arable and silvoarable undiscounted costs and benefits

When we analyse the results of the arable and silvoarable undiscounted costs and benefits, we can observe some clear patterns (Figure 56). For the arable system, the undiscounted non-grant revenue component makes up most of the revenue, due to the low grants considered in the exercise. This non-grant revenue varies according to the harvested crop 2618 £ ha⁻¹ (3016 € ha⁻¹) for winter wheat, 2050 £ ha⁻¹ (2361 € ha⁻¹) for winter barley, 1648 £ ha⁻¹ (1898 € ha⁻¹) for winter oilseed rape, 1148 £ ha⁻¹ (1322 € ha⁻¹) for spring barley, and 1200 £ ha⁻¹ (1382 € ha⁻¹) for winter beans. Arable costs also vary with the cultivated crop, being cyclic

and highest for winter wheat ($1020 \text{ € ha}^{-1} = 1175 \text{ € ha}^{-1}$) and lowest for winter beans ($545 \text{ € ha}^{-1} = 628 \text{ € ha}^{-1}$).

Figure 56. Pattern of arable revenue and costs (left) and pattern of silvoarable revenue and costs (right).

Looking in turn at the silvoarable revenue and costs, the undiscounted non-grant revenue also makes up the bulk of the revenue, due to the low grants considered in the exercise. This non-grant revenue is just over 2000 € ha^{-1} (2304 € ha^{-1}) for the first three years and increases steadily over the next few years according to the increased apple yields, until it reaches a maximum of 6108 € ha^{-1} (7036 € ha^{-1}) on year 10. From then onwards, we can observe the silvoarable revenues decreasing again according to the apple yields harvested but still observing the influence of the crop component on those revenues, ending with values of 3900 € ha^{-1} (4492 € ha^{-1}) and 4958 € ha^{-1} (5711 € ha^{-1}) on years 24 and 25 respectively. Silvoarable costs are highest in the first year 5765 € ha^{-1} (6640 € ha^{-1}) and hover around 2000 € ha^{-1} (2304 € ha^{-1}) for the duration of the cultivation period.

8.3.6 Arable and silvoarable cumulative net margins

We can also observe patterns in the undiscounted and discounted cumulative net margins of the arable and the silvoarable systems (Figure 57). The undiscounted cumulative net margins of the arable system follows a semi-straight line trajectory, from initial values of 1778 € ha^{-1} (2048 € ha^{-1}) in year 1 to final values of 32452 € ha^{-1} (37381 € ha^{-1}) in year 25. The trend in the undiscounted cumulative net margins of the silvoarable system is even more marked and steeper, swiftly changing from initial negative values of -3387 € ha^{-1} (-3902 € ha^{-1}) in years 0-3 to values of 58528 € ha^{-1} (67418 € ha^{-1}) in year 25. The discounted cumulative margins of both systems follow similar trends to the undiscounted cumulative net margins but with a less steep incline, with equal initial values and final values of 21309 € ha^{-1} (24546 € ha^{-1}) for the arable system and values of 34265 € ha^{-1} (39470 € ha^{-1}) at the end of the silvoarable cycle.

Figure 57. Undiscounted cumulative net margins (left) and discounted cumulative net margins (right).

8.3.7 Summary

The tabular summary (

Table 45) shows a summary of the results obtained from the modelling exercise of a silvoarable system at Hope Farm using the Farm-SAFE model. These results were calculated by comparing one hectare of arable and one hectare of the silvoarable system, with a simulation (analysis) period of 25 years and a discount rate of 4%.

If we look at the crop results from individual components of the two systems separately, we can recognise that margins and revenues are generally higher for the arable system compared to the crop only component of the silvoarable system. Due to the crop area of the silvoarable system occupying only 80% of the arable system area and only a minimal planting grant for each of the trees, grants for the arable system were approximately 20% greater than those obtained for the silvoarable system. The undiscounted (4500 £ ha⁻¹) and discounted (2924 £ ha⁻¹) grant revenue for the arable system was thus about 20% higher than that of the combined component of the silvoarable system, which was 3611 £ ha⁻¹ and 2351 £ ha⁻¹ for the undiscounted and discounted grant revenue respectively.

Table 45. Predicted undiscounted, discounted and equivalent annual value (EAV) (discount rate of 4%) of the arable and silvoarable system at Hope Farm.

	Units	Arable system	Silvoarable system		
			Crop	Tree	Combined
Undiscounted net margin	(£ ha ⁻¹)	32452	25961	33782	59744
Undisc. product revenue	(£ ha ⁻¹)	47746	38197	75721	113917
Undisc. grant revenue	(£ ha ⁻¹)	4500	3600	11	3611
Undiscounted costs	(£ ha ⁻¹)	19794	15835	41950	57785
Discounted net margin	(£ ha ⁻¹)	21309	17047	18365	35413
Disc. revenue (excl. grants)	(£ ha ⁻¹)	31293	25034	46429	71463
Discounted grant revenue	(£ ha ⁻¹)	2924	2340	11	2351
Discounted costs	(£ ha ⁻¹)	12908	10327	28075	38402
EAV of net margin	(£ ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹)	1364	1091	1176	2267
EAV of revenue (excl. grants)	(£ ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹)	2003	1602	2972	4575
EAV of grant revenue	(£ ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹)	187	150	1	150
EAV of costs	(£ ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹)	826	661	1797	2458

The combined (crop plus tree) net margin of the silvoarable system surpassed the net margins of the arable system. The undiscounted net margin for the silvoarable system (59744 £ ha⁻¹) was 84% higher than that of the arable system (32452 £ ha⁻¹). The discounted net margin for the combined components of the silvoarable system (35413 £ ha⁻¹) was 66% higher than that of the arable system (21309 £ ha⁻¹). This was in large part due to the expected revenue from the apple trees in the silvoarable system as well as the continued production from the crop component, which was assumed to be unaffected by the apple trees given the wide tree strips and the use of dwarf apple trees that were assumed not to grow beyond 3 m in height. The undiscounted product revenue (113917 £ ha⁻¹) for the silvoarable system was 139% higher than that of the arable system (47746 £ ha⁻¹). The discounted product revenue (71463 £ ha⁻¹) for the combined components of the silvoarable system was 128% higher than that of the arable system (31293 £ ha⁻¹).

8.4 Financial analysis using INTACT

8.4.1 Model and assumptions

The INTACT model is described in the Italian Case Study in Section 4.4. Below, a summary of assumptions made are listed with a few additions for calculating the Italian Living Lab case. All assumptions can be fully read in the manual of INTACT 1.0 ([Agroforestry Planner](#))

- Tree-crop and tree-animal interactions affecting tree yield are not considered. Positive side effects, such as natural pest control or nutrient recycling, are also not taken into account.
- INTACT was initially built to perform a cost-benefit analysis of an alley cropping system but it is possible to use it for other tree spatial arrangements. It is essential that the total tree row surface is calculated well, so INTACT can calculate costs accordingly.

- Pricing for planting materials is based on tree nursery catalogues from 2023. With the Excel INTACT version 1.1, it was possible to adjust the prices but this is not the case for the web tool.
- The surface area of the plot is used to calculate the number of trees per hectare.
- The surface area of the tree rows is used for calculations related to terrain modifications or other planting activities. This distinction was made because these calculations should only be applied to the tree area and not to the entire field.
- Labour (units: h) is based on figures from Normenboek KWIN NL_2020 (van Raffe and de Jong, 2020). INTACT allows users to select their own wage, with the model applying the user's chosen wage to the time required for an activity.
- Machine costs are based on the figures from Normenboek KWIN NL_2020 (van Raffe and de Jong, 2020), but an adjustment of those figures was necessary each time to take out the labour costs, as these are budgeted separately in INTACT (see previous point).
- INTACT calculates labour for terrain modifications based on an average reflecting three soil types (sand, loam, clay) from the Normenboek KWIN NL_2020 (van Raffe and de Jong, 2020). At the moment, it is not possible to let the user choose a soil type to adapt the calculations.
- INTACT calculates fruit and nut yield linearly based on 1) the year at which the tree has reached its maximum production (peak year), and 2) applying the "40-60-80-100% rule" i.e. a simplification of reality implying that yield linearly increases to the peak year and afterward the yield is constant. A tree's peak production year represents 100%. In the year prior, it produces 80%, followed by 60% two years before the peak, and 40% three years before. No yield has been calculated for any years earlier than that. The years following the peak production year are maintained at 100% production through to year 20, the final year of the simulation. Note that the peak year is species-dependent which could be disadvantageous for certain species (e.g. sugar maple) in a timeline of 20 years. Another point of discussion is that yields for slow-growing trees should be more gradually increasing than the 40-60-80-100% rule, whereas this could be the opposite for fast-growing trees. We average this out by applying the 40-60-80-100% rule to all species.
- INTACT assumes that 100% of the tree products is sold.
- Benefits considered are freshly harvested fruits and nuts. Processed fruits and nuts are not included in INTACT 1.0.
- To give insight into wood production, wood yield is shown in a separate table at the final step. However, wood yield is not taken into account in INTACT's cost-benefit analysis. The reason for this is that the financial value of wood yield is volatile and we have yet to work out a more reliable methodology for this. For the Italian Living Lab, the Excel model INTACT version 1.1 was used as wood was the only product.
- We assume that the user completes the steps as accurately as possible to get a realistic estimate of the costs and benefits of his scenario. We advise the user to consult INTACT 1.0 Manual if more background information and web tool tips are desired.

8.4.2 Yield, costs, and price data

Since no model for dwarf apple trees exists within INTACT, the apple yield curve of common apples was used to predict future apple yields for Hope Farm. INTACT calculates yield by applying the “40-60-80-100% rule” (see assumptions above). The highest fruit production year of a fruit tree is referred to its “peak production year”, representing 100%. In the year prior, it produces 80%, followed by 60% two years before the peak, and 40% three years before. No yield was calculated for any years earlier than that. The years following the peak production year are maintained at 100% production through to year 20, which is the final year of the simulation. For apple trees, the peak year is reached at 10, at a yield of 27 kg tree⁻¹ (Figure 58). Regarding the benefits, the apple price was manually adjusted in INTACT to £ 1.1 kg⁻¹ (adopted from Table 43) but this was converted to euros (1.265 € kg⁻¹).

Figure 58. Yield profile per tree for apple (kg tree⁻¹).

For modelling Hope Farm, INTACT used a combination of default data (e.g. from the literature and other financial tools) and from conversations with the farm managers to identify the costs and benefits of production (Table 46).

Table 46. Input table of general information of the Hope Farm silvoarable system.

Inputs	Units
Surface agroforestry plot	11 (ha)
Number of trees	200 (n)
Tree density	83 (n ha ⁻¹)
Expected surface of tree rows	0.6462 (ha)
Gross salary - contractor	129.38* (€ h ⁻¹)
Gross salary – seasonal labour	17.25* (€ h ⁻¹)
Gross salary - farmer	0

*Hope farm data converted to euros with exchange rate of 1 euro = 1.15 pounds.

In Table 47, costs are summarized for the Hope Farm scenario using mostly INTACT's default data.

Table 47. Input table of costs for tree component of the Hope Farm silvoarable system. Default data is shown as grey cells whereas data from Hope Farm is shown without background colouring.

Costs - Investment	Total costs (€ plot⁻¹)	Labour (h plot⁻¹)	Of which labour costs (€ plot⁻¹)
Plant material			
Apple	5 462.50		
Transport	100		
Tree establishment			
Loosen the soil and prepare it for sowing	1 212.54	7.95	1 028.31 ^c
Deep soil preparation	611.48	4.12	532.96 ^c
Sowing tree row	211.31	5.82	0 ^f
Planting - manually ¹	1 137.67	0	3.30
Compost or wood chips ¹	-	-	-
Tree support materials ¹	4 080.00	11.07	0 ^f
Tree protection			
Single or double mesh net (120 cm) ¹	420	3.80	0 ^f
Sheep fence (C 2172 m)	6 617.36	56.04	0 ^f
Costs - Operational	Total costs (€ plot⁻¹ year⁻¹)	Labour (h plot⁻¹ year⁻¹)	Of which labour costs (€ plot⁻¹ year⁻¹)
Tree management			
Mowing around trees ¹	534.26	3.90	504.56 ^c
Monitoring dwarf trees ²	905.63	7.00	905.63 ^c
Monitoring standard trees ²	4 269.38	33.00	4 269.38 ^c
Watering trees ²	300	4.00	0 ^f
Pruning (annual maintenance) ²	0	21.67	0 ^f
Harvesting	0	variable	0 ^f

¹ applied to all trees; ² applied to 100 trees; ^c hourly wage used of contractor; ^s hourly wage used of seasonal labour; ^f hourly wage used of farmer

8.4.3 Results

This cost-benefit analysis evaluates the financial performance of establishing and managing apple trees on cropland, considering only the revenues and costs directly related to apple production. No comparison with alternative land uses or crop yield is included. Results were calculated considering a unit area of 11 ha, a simulation (analysis) period of 20 years and a discount rate of 4%. Table 48 gives a summary of the cash flow lifetime of the apple trees. The model included establishment costs (year 0), annual maintenance costs, revenues from apple yield, and free cash flows as the net of revenues and costs from year 0-20.

Table 48. Cash flow timeline of apple trees for Hope Farm (€). On the left, benefits and costs are both split into annual yield or costs, and cumulative yield or costs. Below, the Free Cash flow (FCF), Discounted Free Cash Flow (DFCF), discount rate, and Cumulative Free Cash Flow (CFCF) are shown.

	Year 0	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	Year 6	Year 7	Year 8	Year 9	Year 10
Benefits											
Fruit and nuts	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5 530	8 294	11 059	13 824
Cumulative yield	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5 530	13 824	24 883	38 707
Costs											
Annual costs	19 853	5 475	5 475	5 475	5 175	5 175	5 175	5 175	5 175	5 175	5 175
Cumulative costs	19 853	25 328	30 803	36 278	41 453	46 628	51 803	56 978	62 153	67 328	72 503
FCF	- 19 853	- 5 475	- 5 475	- 5 475	- 5 175	- 5 175	- 5 175	355	3 119	5 884	8 649
DFCF	- 19 853	- 5 264	- 5 062	- 4 867	- 4 424	- 4 253	- 4 090	269	2 280	4 134	5 843
Discount rate	0.04										
CFCF	- 19 853	- 25 117	- 30 179	- 35 046	- 39 470	- 43 724	- 47 813	- 47 544	- 45 265	- 41 130	- 35 288
	Year 11	Year 12	Year 13	Year 14	Year 15	Year 16	Year 17	Year 18	Year 19	Year 20	Total
Benefits											
Fruit and nuts	13 824	13 824	13 824	13 824	13 824	13 824	13 824	13 824	13 824	13 824	176 947
Cumulative yield	52 531	66 355	80 179	94 003	107 827	121 651	135 475	149 299	163 123	176 947	
Costs											
Annual costs	5 175	5 175	5 175	5 175	5 175	5 175	5 175	5 175	5 175	5 175	124 253
Cumulative costs	77 678	82 853	88 028	93 203	98 378	103 553	108 728	113 903	119 078	124 253	
FCF	8 649	8 649	8 649	8 649	8 649	8 649	8 649	8 649	8 649	8 649	52 694
DFCF	5 618	5 402	5 194	4 995	4 802	4 618	4 440	4 440	4 269	4 105	12 104
Discount rate	0.04										
CFCF	- 29 669	- 24 267	- 19 073	-14 078	- 9 276	- 4 658	- 218	4 052	8 157	12 104	12 104

Apple tree production is estimated to start on year 7 (Figure 59). Accordingly, we see that the revenue from apple yields begins in year 7, matching the cash flow timeline (Table 48.) The Free Cash Flow (FCF) is negative from year 0 to year 6, which is due to the initial investment (€19 5853), and annual costs around €5 175 up to €5 475 each year after that for maintenance. In total, costs add up to €124 253. The FCF becomes positive from year 7 onwards as the apples begin to yield marketable products. From year 10 onwards, peak production is reached, and apple trees bring in about €13 824 every year from fruit sales. In INTACT’s simulation timespan, total earnings from apple production reach, therefore, €176 947.

The total benefits (revenue from apples) amount to €176 947. After all costs (€124 253) are paid, the apple trees leave a net cash return of around €52 694. Even when adjusting for inflation and the time value of money, the investment still shows a positive return of €12 104 over 20 years. The results from Table 48 are shown graphically in Figure 59. The cost-benefit analysis is shown for plot-level, indicating cumulative benefits (revenues from apples), cumulative costs (initial investment at year 0 plus annual maintenance costs).

Figure 59. The cost-benefit analysis of Hope Farm is visualised by providing the cumulative benefits, cumulative costs, and the cumulative free cash flow. The blue arrow indicates the break-even point, whereas the orange arrow shows the payback year.

Looking at the results in Table 48, we can see that the NPV is €12 104, using a discount rate of 4%. This number represents the final cumulative discounted free cash flow. The IRR is 6%, and thereby exceeding the 4% discount rate. The analysis considers an investment cost

(excluding VAT and without subsidies) of € 19 853. The payback period was set on year 18, so 18 years after establishing the apple trees (Figure 59). Lastly, for the benefit: cost ratio, the revenue from apples amount to €176 947, compared to total costs of €124 253, resulting in a benefit: cost ratio of 1 : 1.42 (i.e. more costs are made per euro invested).

Table 49. Results of modelling the Hope Farm case using INTACT.

Financial metrics	Units	Value	Additional info
Default analysis (no apple harvest costs)			
Net present value (4% discount rate)	€	12 104	At a 4% discount rate
Internal rate of return	%	6	Annual return
Investment cost (excl. VAT and subsidy)	€	19 853	One-time investment in Year 0
Payback period	years	18	Based on cumulative free cash flow
Benefit: cost ratio		1 : 1.42	Benefits per €1 invested

The INTACT model predicted that revenue from apple yields begins after 7 years of tree establishment, with full productive output achieved in year 10, generating €13,824 annually through the end of the simulation (year 20). The predicted break-even point was reached after 18 years of tree establishment (year 18), with cumulative discounted free cash flows turning positive from this point onward. The total costs over the 20-year was estimated to be €124 253 (initial investment plus annual maintenance costs), while total benefits (undiscounted) reached about €177 000.

8.5 Reflections on using Farm-SAFE and INTACT in the UK

The Farm-SAFE model was originally designed for silvoarable systems comprising timber trees. Because the agroforestry system at Hope Farm is composed of fruit trees, we found some challenges and had to implement some changes in the original model and adapt it to the case study. These challenges and changes are summarised here:

- We found that the companion Yield-SAFE model to Farm-SAFE needed to be calibrated to determine fruit production by trees.
- Farm-SAFE was originally designed to model forestry species, and it was challenging to incorporate fruit trees. We could only incorporate one fruit tree species at a time in the system.
- The original model did not account for water irrigation costs at the establishment phase of the tree component of the silvoarable system; the model was adapted accordingly to include these costs.
- The original model did not account for packaging costs for the by-product of the tree component of the silvoarable system; the model was adapted accordingly to include these costs.

The INTACT model was designed for understanding the costs of benefits of the tree component only. While working on Hope Farm as a case study, certain challenges and changes are summarised here:

- INTACT can only apply one hourly wage per step (e.g. Tree establishment) but within that step, multiple tasks can be performed by different people (contractor, seasonal labour or farmer) whom all have different hourly wages. This is why INTACT's Excel (English, version 1.1) was used, so manual adjustments could be made.
- INTACT calculates costs based on tree size for e.g. tree establishment (such as digging holes) and tree management (such as monitoring trees). However, the user could only select one tree size per species. As Hope Farm has both dwarf and standard apple trees, INTACT's Excel (English, version 1.1) was changed to provide more freedom in choosing multiple tree sizes per tree species.
- INTACT is a model built for the Belgian and Dutch context, and therefore, units are expressed as euros. However, it is not possible to change all units into pounds at the moment. For certain important context-based values, e.g. hourly wage and the apple price, it was important to use (local) values from Hope Farm. This is why the "UK values" (expressed in £) were converted to euros.
- INTACT does not include costs after picking the apples, i.e. crates to collect apples, cleaning apples, sorting apples, and transport costs are not taken into account. It would be interesting to get more insight into these costs (next steps).

9 Lessons learnt

The development of financial models is an ongoing process. During the process of undertaking the financial analyses described in this report, we improved the capability of some of the models. We also learnt lessons from using the financial models.

9.1 Improvements to the financial models

Farm-SAFE: the model has been adapted to integrate the production of a fruit tree system, in the agroforestry set-up. In addition the model structure has been updated to incorporate the costs of irrigation (to improve tree establishment). The capability to include product package costs for the apples has also been included.

INTACT: during the past 12 months, the Excel sheet associated with the INTACT model has been translated into English. In addition there is the capability to derive an overview of labour requirements. There is also an added option to select multiple species in the Excel version of the model.

AgroForstRechner: an error that caused the application to freeze under certain circumstances, was solved. The plan is now to include AgroForstRechner on the DigitAF tool catalogue.

9.2 Potential future improvements

The use of the financial modelling tools across the six case studies highlighted some potential improvements to each model to make them more useful. However, there is a balance between comprehensiveness and usability; adding improvements can sometimes make the tools too complicated for others to use.

Farm-SAFE: At present a timber version of the model is available on-line. It would be useful to make a fruit-production system model available online. Based on the feedback from the Italian Living Lab, approaches to improve the user-friendliness of the model will be investigated.

INTACT: the Excel model gives the user more freedom, but it is not as user-friendly as the web tool. Therefore, it would be beneficial to offer the users greater flexibility in the web tool by adding more adjustable selection fields. This would allow the users to modify prices for planting material, tree protection, but also for labour (e.g. more types of labour or a percentage of labour allocated to farmer/contractor/seasonal labour).

Increasing the simulation time window would make the model more appropriate to analyse systems aiming for timber production of slow-growing tree species. Also, it would be ideal if INTACT had a map interface. This would allow users to draw a map, and insert google maps location (i.e. like in CARAT)

9.3 Improving the FAIR scores of the models

A major area of progress with some of the models is to make the model more readily available online with associated manuals. This has been a major activity in terms of the Farm-SAFE and INTACT models, where the models have been referenced in the DigitAF [tool catalogue](#) and a FAIR score has been established (

Table 50).

Table 50. The findability, accessibility, interoperability, reusability scores of the six financial models as assessed on the DigitAF tool database <https://digitaf.eu/tools-data-and-projects-catalogue/tools>.

Tool	Findability	Accessibility	Interoperability	Reusability
Farm-SAFE	67%	70%	88%	100%
Rekentool	67%	70%	47%	55%
AgroForstRechnung	-	-	-	-
Final ALS	-	-	-	-
INTACT	67%	91%	28%	63%
FarmTree	67%	97%	77%	63%

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Appendix A. Metadata describing attributes of six agroforestry financial models

Table 51. Metadata table describing attributes of six agroforestry financial models

Model name	Farm-SAFE v3	Rekenmodel agroforestry v1.01 Oct 2023 (HAF)	Agroforstrechner (AF-R)	INTACT 1.0	FINAL -ALS	FarmTree Tool
Entry completed by	Paul Burgess	Waas Thissen	Rico Hübner	Sarah Carton	Jaroslav Knápek, Jan Weger	Marina Alarcón, Frank van Schoubroeck
General features						
Timestep	Annual	Annual	Annual	Annual	Annual	Monthly and Annual
Typical duration of simulation	60 years	50 years	80 years	20 years	30 years	50 years
Currency (euro, pound, ...)	Currently set to £ but could be €	€	€	€	Currently set to CZK but could be €	Multiple currencies
Discount methodology	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes.	Yes.
Spatial scale	Plot and Farm	Plot	Plot	Plot	Whole Plantation (AFS)	Plot and Farm
number of systems that can be combined/compared	3 (Agroforestry, agriculture, tree-only)				2 (AFS, conventional agriculture)	Multiple
Software/user interface (Excel, Python, R, Oracle Apex, ...)	Microsoft Excel		Excel (old version) / Python (new)	Excel (database) and Oracle Apex (interface)	Microsoft Excel	software: .NET (C#, Blazor) tool interface: currently Blazor, will be replaced by React output downloads: Excel / csv / png; API: under construction (using json)
Target group (end user)	Researcher and possibly Advisor		Farmers, farm advisors and other experts	Farmers, farm advisors, investor/project manager,	Researcher, advisor, investor, farmer	advisor, investor, farmer, researcher

	Farm-SAFE v3	Rekenmodel agroforestry	Agroforstrechner (AF-R)	INTACT 1.0	FINAL -ALS	FarmTree Tool
System description						
how is the context defined (country, region, exact location on a map)?	No context	No context	Focus on Brandenburg, DE	Focus on Flanders	originally Czech Republic	User selects exact location by specifying plot/farm coordinates, which automatically links to site-specific climate and soil data. Price and cost data (database) is country/region specific.
How is the agroforestry system described (tree species, tree density, crop rotation, animal species...)?	Tree species, tree density, crop rotation	Tree species, density, starting year planting	tree species, crop rotation	Tree species, tree density	Area (ha), tree density, conventional crop rotation	Perennials: species, density, year of planting. Annuals: species, % plot cover, crop rotation
How is tree management described (pruning, thinning, harvest...): please add the type of info (date, number of operations, products used etc...)	pruning:, thinning:, harvest:	No		Mulching, pruning, thinning, harvesting, weeding, mowing, and watering	All necessary operations can be included	Mulching, pruning, thinning, harvesting, watering, fertilising/compost
How is crop management described: please add the type of info (date, number of operations, products used etc...)	Seed cost, fertilizer cost, labour and management cost			No	All necessary operations can be included	1) Aggregated initial labour and costs per species or input (year of planting): seeds/seedlings costs, land preparation, planting, infrastructure set up. 2) Aggregated running labour and costs per species or input (yearly): weeding, watering, fertilising, infrastructure repairs. 3) Labour for harvest per species (not all years)

	Farm-SAFE v3	Rekenmodel agroforestry	Agroforstrechner (AF-R)	INTACT 1.0	FINAL -ALS	FarmTree Tool
Productivity						
Crop productivity	Crop yields derived from Yield-SAFE or equivalent	No		No	Crops yields from national statistics	Crop yields derived from FarmTree Model
Animal productivity	Grass yields derived from Yield-SAFE or equivalent	No		No	No	No
Tree productivity	Tree yields derived from Yield-SAFE or equivalent	Yes		Yes	Selected yield curves from Czech Republic	Tree yields derived from FarmTree Model, regionally calibrated with literature, expert and field data
Carbon storage	Tree carbon derived from Yield-SAFE or equivalent	No	No	No	No	Carbon stored (perennials) derived from FarmTree Model, regionally calibrated with literature, expert and field data
other ecosystem services (please detail)	Values can be derived from Yield-SAFE but currently not included	No		No	No - but would like to try to include erosion control effect	Yes - erosion mitigation, water infiltration, biodiversity index, NPK and SOM accumulation, pest pressure reduction
Prices						
Grain/tuber	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Biomass	No	No	Yes	No	Yes (woodchips)	Yes
Other crop products	One byproduct	No		No	optionally straw	Fodder, Straw
Fruits	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Nuts	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Timber	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Other tree products	Woodfuel	Possible		Not in version 1.0	NO	Fuelwood
Meat, milk or eggs	No	No	No	No	No	No
Carbon credits	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Subsidies	Yes	Yes		Not in version 1	Yes (CAP SAPS or others if available)	Not currently available

	Farm-SAFE v3	Rekenmodel agroforestry	Agroforstrechner (AF-R)	INTACT 1.0	FINAL -ALS	FarmTree Tool
Costs						
Land	No	Yes		No	Yes	No
Labour	Yes	Yes		Yes.	Yes	Yes.
machinery	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes, as a service	Yes
Tree seedlings, crop seeds...)	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Water	No	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Fuel	Yes, included under machinery	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes, included in aggregated running costs per species (yearly)
Pesticides and fertilisers	Yes				Yes	Yes
Tree protection	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Discount rate	Determined by user			0.04	Determined by user	0.1 (default)
Outputs						
Cost	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Revenue	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Gross margin	Yes	Yes		No	Yes	Yes
Net margin	Yes			Yes	Yes	No
Workload	Yes (annual)	No		Yes	No	Yes, monthly and yearly
NPV (net present value)	Yes			Yes	Yes	Yes
IRR (internal rate of return)	Can be inferred			Yes	No	Yes
Break-even point	Can be inferred			Yes	Yes	Yes
Benefit: cost ratio	Yes			Yes	Yes	No, but can be easily included
ROI (return on investment)	Can be inferred			No		No, but can be easily included

	Farm-SAFE v3	Rekenmodel agroforestry	Agroforstrechner (AF-R)	INTACT 1.0	FINAL -ALS	FarmTree Tool
Other characteristics						
Time period	Planting to harvest of trees	Whole life cycle		Whole life cycle	from planting to harvest	Whole life cycle
Primary focus	Financial cost benefit analysis	Financial cost benefit analysis		Partial, financial cost-benefit analysis	Financial cost benefit analysis	Mainly ex-ante financial cost benefit analysis and ecosystem services analysis
Components taken into account	Tree and crop	Tree		Tree	Tree and crop	Perennials and annuals
type of systems that can be modelled	Arable, Forestry, Agroforestry			Alley cropping systems or orchards	Silvoarable AFS and crops	Arable, Forestry, Agroforestry
Website	https://dspace.lib Cranfield.ac.uk/handle/1826/22350	https://www.wur.nl/project/pps-verdienmodellen-agroforestry.htm	https://agroforst-info.de/agroforstrechner/	Agroforestry Planner - Agroforestry	No	https://tool.farmtree.earth/
Videos available: Yes (and location) /No	Not yet		Not yet	Recorded; waiting for upload on Youtube	Under preparation (VI/25)	
User Manual available	Yes https://dspace.lib Cranfield.ac.uk/handle/1826/22350		Yes https://agroforst-info.de/agroforstrechner/	Agroforestry Planner - Agroforestry	Methodology+ manual Under preparation (XII/25)	
climate change	No, but can be completed in Yield-SAFE			No	Yes -partially	
system design	Tree density; thinning analysis			No	No	

Appendix B. Full qualitative evaluation of Farm-SAFE and INTACT tools in Italy

Table 52. Complete qualitative evaluation of Farm-SAFE and INTACT tools performed from Labs participants.

App		Marks (1-5)		What would you improve about the tool?		Does the tool help you solve your problems? If no, what specific problems does it solve instead?		How would you improve the usability of the tool?	
Stakeholder/User		Farm-SAFE	INTACT	Farm-SAFE	INTACT	Farm-SAFE	INTACT	Farm-SAFE	INTACT
1	Farmer	2	3	Reduction of the amount of data required	Insert mediterranean species; less bugs; it did not reveal the value of timber at the end of the simulation	Too complicated to be used by farmers	Various options, it allows to explore several technical choices	User interface	Description of specific use of the tree species present
2	Advisor	4	4	Improve the user interface	When choosing the tree species, separation between forest trees, urban trees, and fruit trees or shrubs (easier to find the tree of interest, at the moment they are all mixed). In general, better separation/classification of the available choices	Useful as decision support system, particularly to evaluate future investments	A better projection of the investment; the results are difficult to interpret;	User interface; Some of the parameters automatically calculated; Reduce the amount of farm data required	I would limit it to agricultural and forest use; to improve in the choice of soil operation and system management
3	Advisor/Researcher	4	5		Insert the possibility of give a slope to the field; include other tree species (Mediterranean adaptation)		It does not allow to evaluate the herbaceous crop		Include other languages; Include Google Maps (like CARAT)
4	Farmer	1	4	User interface; Data requirement;	Include animals; Include Mediterranean species; Adapt to region/countries to select a proper price	It could be solving some problem but it require too	Yes, possibility to make a prevision of	Creation of a software instead of excel; Some of	Possibility to draw the filed with tree spatial

				Simplify the usability		many data; some difficulties in reading the results	costs in few time	the data should be inserted automatically to reduce the amount of data required	distribution and fences; Other languages
5	Farmer	3	4	Usability	Include the possibility to use a map; Language				Include more tree species
6	Advisor	3	2	Usability	Include a higher amount of trees available; Include animal component; Possibility to change the cost	It solves some problems but not feasible to use it everyday	No, difficulties to apply it in a typical Italian situation	Smarter app; easier to understand	Possibility to integrate some other data; possibility to draw the field
7	Farmer	4	2	Usability	Increase the possibility to insert data depending on the local situation	Yes	No, it does not help to build a realistic project	User interface; simplified for farmers	
8	Advisor	2	3	Usability	Usability, bugs; Increase the possibility of tree selection; Include animals				More languages